

APPROVED: 27 May 2026
doi: 10.2903/sp.efsa.2026.EN-9516

Report of the Third International Workshop on Horizon Scanning for Plant Health

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), French
Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational
Health & Safety (ANSES) and European Commission
– Joint Research Centre (JRC)

Abstract

This report is dedicated to the Third International Workshop on Horizon Scanning for Plant Health, held on 02-04th December 2025, at the ANSES headquarters in Maisons-Alfort, France. The main objective of this third workshop was the identification of risk drivers for plant pests. The event was attended by experts on foresight, risk detection and scientists on plant health, for a total of 27 people in person and other 10 speakers from remote. During the two full days meeting, presentations were delivered to and by participants, a polycrisis exercise was driven by JRC and a series of activities were performed in order to integrate all the knowledge acquired. The take-home messages collected during the event are summarized at the end of the report.

© European Food Safety Authority, French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety, 2026

Keywords: foresight, horizon scanning, One Health, polycrisis, risk drivers.

Question number: EFSA-Q-2026-00269

Correspondence: any enquiries related to this output should be addressed to plants@efsa.europa.eu

Acknowledgements: EFSA wishes to thank ANSES and JRC for their role in the organisation and success of the event, and all participants for their contributions.

Suggested citation: EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), ANSES (French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety) and JRC (European Commission – Joint Research Centre), 2026. Report of the Third International Workshop on Horizon Scanning for Plant Health. Paris, 02-04th December 2025. EFSA Supporting publication 2026: EN-10143. 58 pp. doi:10.2903/sp.efsa.2026.EN-10143

ISSN: 2397-8325

© European Food Safety Authority, 2026

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Summary

Since 2017, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) is mandated by the European Commission (EC) to conduct horizon scanning (HS) in the field of plant health. This task is performed in collaboration with the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the EC (under a series of service-level agreements (SLAs)) and with the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES) (under grant GP/EFSA/PLANTS/2022/07).

The HS activity is conducted by capturing signals from the web about potential threats represented by plant pests from all around the world, analysing them and sharing the results with EU risk managers in order to support their preparedness and timely reactions. More than 140 newsletters, three technical reports and two event reports have been published so far.

This type of activity, based on quickly evolving technologies and conceived to be conducted in a continuous and rapid manner, requires frequent updates of methods and tools and regular interaction with stakeholders. For these reasons, a series of workshops have been devoted to HS, targeting different groups of experts and topics each time.

The First International Workshop on Horizon Scanning for Plant Health was held on the 9-10th April 2024 in the headquarters of ANSES (Maisons-Alfort, France). This first occasion allowed risk assessors and, more in general, experts on invasive species and plant pests to share experiences and map current knowledge and practices devoted to identifying emerging threats. One of the main conclusions of the event was the need to involve decision makers in the identification of the most suitable tools and methods to support timely action with horizon scanning techniques.

The Second International Workshop on Horizon Scanning for Plant Health, was targeted at plant health risk managers. The event was held in the headquarters of ANSES on 11-13th February 2025 and focused on the identification of needs and priorities of final users of HS outputs, from plant protection officers to decision makers. The feedback received during that workshop helped improving the outputs produced by the HS activity and set off the creation of the first Plant Health Community of Epidemic intelligence from open sources (EIOS) system¹.

In consideration of the outcomes from both events, the third workshop, reported here, was conceived to explore the concept of risk drivers. The aim was to investigate the potential for the plant health HS to integrate risk factors interacting with pest invasion events. The Third International Workshop on Horizon Scanning for Plant Health was held in Maison Alfort on 2-4th December 2025 with experts on foresight and risk detection. This report provides the main content and outcomes of the workshop, the list of participants, the agenda, brief summaries of the presentations, results of the interactive sessions, and conclusions with future perspectives.

¹ The automatic public health surveillance platform [EIOS \(Epidemic Intelligence from Open Sources\)](#), born from the collaboration between WHO and JRC.

Table of contents

Abstract	1
Summary	3
Table of contents	4
Introduction	5
Objective of the workshop	6
Participants	6
Presentations and references	6
Introduction and welcoming presentations by ANSES and EFSA:	7
JRC presentations:	8
Participants’ presentations:.....	25
Challenge of the workshop	44
Polycrisis exercise.....	44
Interactive session results	49
Dynamic wrap up/overview	52
Conclusions and recommendations	54
Abbreviations	55
Appendix A– List of participants	56
Appendix B– Agenda of the event	57

Introduction

Since 2017, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), at the request of the European Commission (EC), has been conducting horizon scanning (HS hereinafter) in the field of plant health. This initiative is currently carried out in collaboration with the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the EC and the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES). The primary task is to capture web signals from media and scientific literature about potential threats caused worldwide by plant pests. The information is gathered using Epidemic intelligence from open sources (EIOS) system, a text mining tool provided by World Health Organization (WHO) in collaboration with JRC where more than 90 countries and 25 organisations and networks are actively involved. The signals are filtered and delivered to EU risk managers on a monthly basis, in support of their preparedness and timely reactions. The monthly results are both summarized on a newsletter published in the EFSA Journal² and in an interactive dashboard³ on the EFSA website. They include details on the source of the information and on the biology and ecology of the mentioned pests, furthermore, are highlighted the most relevant signals of the month and the results of the fast risk screening (PeMo) performed on pests identified for the first time during the HS activity. The PeMo targets pests that are not regulated at EU level, not included in EPPO lists, and have not been assessed by other official bodies yet.

In the context of the partnership renewed between EFSA and ANSES from 2022 to 2026 (EFSA Art 36 grant GP/EFSA/PLANTS/2022/07), a series of workshops and webinars have been planned to be held between 2024 and 2026. Their objectives are to: i) support the dissemination of the EFSA HS approach; ii) ensure the timely communication of HS results; and iii) strengthen global HS in Plant Health by initiating a worldwide community.

The first⁴ and second⁵ workshops helped to improve the HS tools, methods and outputs thanks to the participation and contribution of risk assessors and risk managers respectively. Following the second event, the first Plant Health Community of EIOS was successfully launched. This third event was conceived to explore the concept of risk drivers. The aim was to investigate the potential for the plant health HS to integrate risk factors able to influence pest invasion processes. The screening of events that have an implication in pests' dispersal and impact, before the appearance of a new outbreak, is expected to further enhance preparedness of risk managers.

This report includes the list of participants, the agenda, summaries of the presentations and the interactive sessions, and conclusions with future perspectives. The involvement of participants

² All horizon scanning newsletters are freely available at the following [link](#)

³ The horizon scanning dashboard for plant pests is freely available at the following [link](#)

⁴ Agence Nationale de Sécurité Sanitaire de l'Alimentation, de l'Environnement et du Travail, European Food Safety Authority, Joint Research Centre, European Commission, Tramontini, S., Ribaya Muñoz, M., Larenaudie, M., Gachet, E., Vos, S., Doherty, B., López Mercadal, J. (2024). Report of the First International Workshop on Horizon Scanning for Plant Health. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13939336>

⁵ Agence Nationale de Sécurité Sanitaire de l'Alimentation, de l'Environnement et du Travail, European Food Safety Authority, Joint Research Centre, European Commission, Tramontini, S., Bellenot, C., Pochlauer, D., Ribaya Muñoz, M., Gachet, E., Vos, S., López Mercadal, J., Reignault, P. (2025). Report of the Second International Workshop on Horizon Scanning for Plant Health. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15696756>

with different areas of expertise and knowledge helped to identify and define potential risk drivers for plant health and to move towards a One Health approach.

Objective of the workshop

Currently, our HS activity targets plant pest species, mentioned whenever a new event occurs (new host plant, new geographic distribution, new detection method, etc). However, in an effort to increase our ability to anticipate threats, we seek to identify other signs/weak signals that can provide preliminary indications of potentially significant emerging issues before impacts are recorded. There are many factors that may support the arrival, establishment, spread or impact of a pest, and it is important to identify and classify them to understand their role in these events, with the final goal of further increasing preparedness. In addition, certain risks that may not have a direct effect on plant health must be considered, as the cascade phenomenon between events is common. Therefore, this workshop gathered experts on foresight and risk drivers, from different expertise areas, aiming to identify new risk drivers for plant pests.

Participants

The event was co-organised by EFSA and ANSES, hosted by ANSES and chaired by JRC. The composition of the audience can be divided into remote speakers (10), in person participants and organisers (27), coming from a total of 15 institutions and 10 different countries. In Appendix A, the full list of contributors, with affiliation and role during the event, is provided.

The remote speakers were all from the JRC and their contribution, although essential, was limited to the moment of their intervention, dedicated to giving an insight about the different risk areas of study in the different units, with a specific focus to risk drivers.

The in-person participants came from academia and public institutions and were selected for their particular involvement in foresight activities in different areas, ranging from animal health to invasive species, from epidemiology to entomology.

Since the idea was to provide a brief overview of different topics with a view to subsequently identifying the risk factors for plant pests, the presentations were limited to between 10 and 15 minutes. This allowed all participants to share their work, in an oral presentation or a poster. All presentations are summarised in the following section.

Presentations and references

The presentations delivered during this workshop are summarised below and the material shared by speakers is accessible from the same link where this report is stored, under the community “Knowledge Junction” of Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20425716>

Introduction and welcoming presentations by ANSES and EFSA:

Philippe Reignault – ANSES / Head of the Plant Health Laboratory & Scientific Director for Plant Health

Topic: Description of French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES)

Summary: ANSES may be considered a One Health agency due to the variety of covered topics (i.e., animal health and welfare; plant, environmental and occupational health; food safety). Taking a multidisciplinary approach that engages with more than 800 experts from different fields, ANSES' missions rely on the production of knowledge, alerts and assessments on health risks. For this purpose, ANSES accounts for six thematic and technical units in the field of plant health: i) Bacteriology, virology & GMO detection (Angers), ii) Entomology & botany (Montpellier), iii) Mycology (Nancy), iv) Nematology (Rennes), v) Quarantine (Clermont-Ferrand), and vi) Tropical pests (Saint-Pierre, Reunion Island), and a seventh unit dedicated to risk assessment: the Biological risk assessment unit, based in Angers, that is involved in the production of pest risk assessments and in the HS activity, this last done in collaboration with EFSA.

Keywords: France, One Health, risk assessment

References:

ANSES. (2026). ANSES - Agence Nationale de Sécurité Sanitaire de l'alimentation, de l'environnement et du Travail. ANSES. <https://www.anses.fr/en>

ANSES. (2026). Expert Assessment of Biological Risks (ERB) unit (Angers site) of the Plant Health Laboratory. ANSES. <https://www.anses.fr/en/content/expert-assessment-biological-risks-erb-unit-angers-site-plant-health-laboratory>

Sybrein Vos – EFSA / Team Leader Plant Health Monitoring

Topic: Description of European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

Summary: EFSA, based in Parma (Italy), was established by the Regulation (EC) No 178/2002⁶ and since then acts as the reference body for the EC, providing risk assessments covering all aspects of the food chain (from plant health to nutrition) for the European Union. Specifically, in the area of plant health, the main objective is to protect both agricultural and natural environments from invasive plant pests. EFSA aims to support EU Member States prevent pest introduction and spread by offering early warning and detection systems that protect crops, forests, and wild species. EFSA has developed a harmonised Plant Health framework, promoting harmonised and consistent phytosanitary protection across the EU. The Plant Health Monitoring Team, in particular, is devoted to three main subjects: i) HS for plant pests, ii) prioritisation of pests, iii) early detection tools.

Keywords: European Union, horizon scanning, plant health, prevention

⁶ Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2002 laying down the general principles and requirements of food law, establishing the European Food Safety Authority and laying down procedures in matters of food safety. OJ L 031 , 01/02/2002 P. 0001 - 0024

References:

EFSA. (2026a). EFSA's subscription centre. EFSA. <https://connect.efsa.europa.eu/RM/SubscriptionCenter>

EFSA. (2026b). EFSA | Science, safe food, sustainability. EFSA. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en>

EFSA. (2026c). Plant health. EFSA. <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/topics/topic/plant-health>

JRC presentations:

This section refers to a series of short speeches given on Day 1 by JRC experts, on a broad set of topics: the scope was to allow participants to get in contact with aspects of risk not necessarily typical or expected in the plant health context and to provide food for thoughts in preparation for the polycrisis exercise of Day 2.

Rui Catarino D.5. - Food Security

Topic: The Aggregated Total Applied Toxicity indicator (ATAT)

Summary: Pesticides have an impact on biodiversity and ecosystem services, which in turn can affect food productivity. To support the headline Indicator 7.2 under Target 7 (i.e., reduction of 50% of pollution) established under the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (CBD, 2022), a harmonised metric, the Aggregated Total Applied Toxicity (ATAT), has been adopted. ATAT converts active-substance use into toxicity-weighted doses per surface unit (Bub *et al.*, 2023; Schulz *et al.*, 2021; Wolfram *et al.*, 2026), using State-level pesticide sales (or use) data together with harmonised ecotoxicological thresholds for the relevant non-target species groups derived from the Pesticide Properties DataBase (PPDB; Lewis *et al.*, 2016). The ATAT is therefore a signal of potential biodiversity hazard obtained at a relatively low cost to MSs but with a strong potential for performing comparative and trend analysis. It enables the comparison of results across years, countries, active substances and different taxonomic groups. For example, preliminary results for France show that, while the pesticide pressure on bees has substantially declined over the last nine years (related to the positive effects of neonicotinoids bans), it remained constant or even slightly increasing for other non-target terrestrial arthropods and aquatic vertebrates. The possibility to aggregate results in different manners makes ATAT a valuable tool, beyond CBD reporting, with relevance across multiple policies and spatial scales. As Parties, each EU MSs and the EU (using aggregated data), are responsible for calculating and reporting its own respective results. At this stage, JRC is testing this indicator with 14 MSs, and building the capacity needed to support them in the preparation and delivery of national ATAT reports under the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.

Keywords: indicator, pesticide, scalability, taxa, toxicity

References:

Bub, S., Wolfram, J., Petschick, L.L., Stehle, S. & Schulz, R., 2023. Trends of total applied pesticide toxicity in German agriculture. *Environmental Science & Technology* 57, 852–861. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.2c07251>

Carneseccchi, E., Mostrag, A., Ciacci, A., Roncaglioni, A., Tarkhov, A., Gibin, D., Sartori, L., Benfenati, E., Yang, C. & Dorne, J. L. C. M. (2023). *OpenFoodTox*: EFSA's chemical hazards database (Version 6) [Data set]. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8120114>

European Commission. (2026). EU Pesticides Database—Active substances [Database]. *EU Pesticides Database*. <https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database/start/screen/active-substances>

Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework: Decision / adopted by the Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity. (2022, December 19). United Nations. Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity (15th: 2021-2022: Kunming, China; Montréal, Canada and Nairobi). *United Nations Digital Library* <https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/4080812>

Lewis, K.A., Tzilivakis, J., Warner, D.J. & Green, A., 2016. An international database for pesticide risk assessments and management. *Human and Ecological Risk Assessment: An International Journal* 22, 1050–1064. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10807039.2015.1133242>

Schulz, R., Bub, S., Petschick, L.L., Stehle, S. & Wolfram, J., 2021. Applied pesticide toxicity shifts toward plants and invertebrates, even in GM crops. *Science* 372, 81–84. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abe1148>

University of Hertfordshire. (2026). The PPDB [Database]. *Pesticide Properties Database*. <https://sitem.herts.ac.uk/aeru/ppdb/en/index.htm>

USEPA (United States Environmental Protection Agency). (2025). ECOTOX knowledge base [Database]. *EPA*. <https://cfpub.epa.gov/ecotox/>

Lia Orfei S.4 - Exploratory Research Programme

Topic: Threats without borders: mosquito modelling for anticipatory risk analysis.

Summary: The presented activity is handled by a team belonging to the Digital Health Unit of JRC, as part of the ETOHA (Emerging Health Threats and the One Health Approach) project. The emerging health threats are handled in line with the One Health principle (Grobert *et al.*, 2024) in order to recognise their interconnectedness across all sectors. In this context, drivers are shared among those sectors, and the plant health sector, in particular, plays a crucial role in providing food security, nutrition and ecosystem stability. Cross-border health threats are of major importance in the JRC activity, as evidenced by the fact that 7 (over the total number of 25) portfolios are involved in it. The quantitative epidemiology falls under the portfolio 14 (Societal resilience, systemic disruptive events and risks: enhancing anticipation, preparedness and responses) and in the process three main steps are identified: i) HS, ii) quantitative risk analysis and iii) spatial/temporal modelling. This activity is applicable to different fields, such as the exercise on *Aedes albopictus*, the Asian tiger mosquito, known to be responsible of dengue outbreaks in the EU (304 cases in 2024 only). Increasingly favourable climate conditions are known to happen in the EU, and early warning activities require the application of climate models. Those models are fed by climate data from Copernicus programme and entomological surveillance data from VectorNet (ECDC and EFSA) and are based on Neural Networks (**AI** *Aedes*)

to predict presence and abundance (in terms of weekly egg-laying rate) of the invasive species. The approach described for mosquitoes is suitable to the plant health domain too, in relation to the processes of i) vectors transmitting pathogens, ii) climate driving range of expansion, iii) surveillance planning, iv) trade and travel accelerating spread.

The COVID-19 pandemic has shown how global threats act as an interconnected web. Four pathways well represent the complexity of this network, where plant health failure affects: i) food security, ii) pollution (by pesticides and chemicals), iii) ecosystems collapse (i.e. biodiversity and carbon sequestration loss), iv) land use change, as summarized in the EC report involving more than 100 scientists assessing 47 risks (Lentini *et al.*, 2025). Therefore, by protecting plant health, the entire web of human, animal, and environmental health is safeguarded.

Keywords: *Aedes albopictus*, global threats, One Health, preparedness, vectors

References:

European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, European Commission: Group of Chief Scientific Advisors, Grobert, N., Ellemers, N., Kruusmaa, M., Lambin, E. F., Melloni, A., Nakićenović, N. & Zažímalová, E. (2024). One Health governance in the European Union. *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/8697309>

European Commission: Joint Research Centre, Lentini, A., Eklund, G., Corbane, C., Asikainen, T., Ronco, M., Urso G., Poljansek, K., Soler Garrido, J., Griesinger, C.B., Reina, V., Spigolon, R., Steri, G., Linge, J., Kotseva, B., Masante, D., Santini, M., Proietti, C., Barantiev, D., Salvitti, V., Destro, E., Mastronunzio, M., Hrast Essenfelder, A., Toreti, A., Salamon, P., D'Angelo, C., Vousdoukas, M., Crippa, M., Pisoni, E., Belis, C., Carravieri, A., Ruiz-Orejón, L.F., Mendes, C., Robuchon, M., Sanchez Arjona, I., Tsionis, G., Schuh, L., Spagnolo, L., Orfei L., Petrillo M., Kephelopoulos, S., Coecke, S., Aschberger, K., Schirinzi, G., Maddalon, A., Valsesia, A., Armas, F., Guglielmelli, A., De La Rosa Blul, J.C., Magrotti, G., Cardarilli, M., Petit, F., Theron, J., De Angelis, A., Krausmann, E., Wood, M., Van Wijk, L., Koutelos, K., Schvitz, G., Galariotis, I., Gentile, C., De Girolamo, L., Duta, A., Caravaggi, I., Thau, A., Bagi, J., Larcher, M., Karlos, V., Ruiz Moreno, A., Baruth, B., Rembold, F., Sedano, F., Scionti, N., San-Miguel, J., Durrant, T., Boca, R., Maianti, P., Oom, D., Branco, A., De Rigo, D., Suarez Moreno, M., Ferrari, D., Roglia, E., Broglia, M., Belmonte, M., Pingsdorf, J., Kajander, N., Majorano Sarapo, F., Greidanus, H., Montanari, E., Piccinini, P., Roman-Cuesta, R.M., Dentener, F., Galmarini, S., De Groeve, T. & Maenhout, G. (2025). Analysis of risks Europe is facing: An analysis of current and emerging risks. *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/0176850>

European Commission. (2024). Platform foR European Preparedness Against (Re-)emerging Epidemics FP7. *CORDIS. EU Research Results*. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/602525/reporting>

VectorNet, European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, & European Food Safety Authority. (2025). *VectorNet observations* (Version 1.5) [Occurrence dataset]. *VectorNet*. <https://doi.org/10.15468/f3k8r9>

Jens Linge T.5. - Data Intelligence for Policy

Topic: Analysis of disinformation narratives using AI

Summary: The analysis of disinformation narratives presented here can be performed on any topic and type of event, although most efforts are currently targeted to public health, elections, migration, biodiversity, Ukraine invasion, and climate change.

Two Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods are utilized: i) multilingual clustering and ii) text classification. First, multilingual clustering groups texts into distinct stories. Large Language Models (LLMs) are then used to summarize the information and extract keywords. Because these summaries are not subject to copyright restrictions, they can be freely shared. Second, for text classification, a machine learning model is trained using predefined data (e.g., known narratives, harmful framing, and persuasion techniques) to perform specific analytical tasks. This approach is exemplified in a COVID-19 publication where 34,000 texts were annotated (Kotseva et al., 2023). When applied to climate change between 2023 and 2024, overarching "super-narratives" were identified, such as "CO2 is beneficial" or "CO2 is not polluting." These narratives can then be clustered by topic and tracked over time. For example, out of ten identified clusters, one focuses on the "Impact of climate change on marine ecosystems and wildlife." By finding similarities, the narratives within this cluster can be grouped into: i) Greenland's polar bears adapting to warming temperatures and other dramatic effects on wildlife; ii) fish species shrinking in size or hybridizing to reduce vulnerability; and iii) contrasting reports on coral reefs, such as the disappearance of coral in the Florida Keys versus reefs successfully handling global warming. Furthermore, the system allows for the comparison of narratives in mainstream media versus unverified sources. This can be done at a macro level across major topics (e.g., during the timeframe from COP27 to COP30) or at a granular level by analysing specific framing dimensions. For instance, during COP meetings, mainstream media primarily framed discussions around "capacity and resources," whereas unverified sources relied heavily on a "political" frame. Ultimately, thousands of articles are collected to identify signals and detect peaks related to a specific subject. Subsequent analysis of these events establishes the exact timeline for each cluster, allowing researchers to track the top stories (typically 20 to 30) over time. Overall, the use of these AI tools enables the processing of massive volumes of data, the removal of duplicates, and the rapid identification of anomalies.

Keywords: clustering, disinformation, misinformation, media analysis

References:

Kotseva, B., Vianini, I., Nikolaidis, N., Faggiani, N., Potapova, K., Gasparro, C., Steiner, Y., Scornavacche, J., Jacquet, G., Dragu, V., Della Rocca, L., Bucci, S., Podavini, A., Verile, M., Macmillan, C. & Linge, J. P. (2023). Trend analysis of COVID-19 mis/disinformation narratives—A 3-year study. *PLoS ONE*, 18(11), e0291423. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0291423>

Pieter Beck D.1. - Land and Climate

Topic: The future distribution of tree species in Europe.

Summary: In 2016, the JRC published the European atlas of forest tree species (San-Miguel-Ayanz *et al.* 2016). It provides ecological information and maps of the current distribution of more than 60 tree species in Europe. Work since then at the JRC modelled also the future distribution of several tree species in Europe based on parameters derived from climate simulations (Mauri *et al.* 2022). The resulting maps show where tree species may find newly suitable habitat by the end of the 21st century, and where tree species may be lost. Combining the predictions for individual tree species allows for estimates of changes in potential species richness. This reveals that certain areas may see species diversity and ecosystem services decline if species are left to only disperse naturally (Mauri *et al.* 2023). Assisted tree migration can help reduce this loss of species richness and ecosystem services.

Keywords: climate change, climate suitability, ecosystem services, diversity loss, species distribution

References:

Mauri, A., Girardello, M., Strona, G., Beck, P. S. A., Forzieri, G., Caudullo, G., Manca, F. & Cescatti, A. (2022). EU-Trees4F, a dataset on the future distribution of European tree species. *Scientific Data*, 9(37). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01128-5>

Mauri, A., Girardello, M., Forzieri, G., Manca, F., Beck, P. S. A., Cescatti, A. & Strona, G. (2023). Assisted tree migration can reduce but not avert the decline of forest ecosystem services in Europe. *Global Environmental Change*, 80, 102676. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2023.102676>

San-Miguel-Ayanz, J., De Rigo, D., Caudullo, G., Houston Durrant, T. & Mauri, A. (Eds). (2016). European atlas of forest tree species. *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/776635>

Wessely, J., Essl, F., Fiedler, K., Gattringer, A., Hülber, B., Ignateva, O., Moser, D., Rammer, W., Dullinger, S. & Seidl, R. (2024). A climate-induced tree species bottleneck for forest management in Europe. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 8, 1109–1117. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-024-02406-8>

Ana Cristina Cardoso D.6. - Nature Conservation and Observations

Topic: Invasive alien species and biodiversity

Summary: Invasive alien species (IAS) are organisms introduced outside their natural range that threaten or adversely impact biodiversity and related ecosystem services. Certain IAS- those listed as IAS of Union concern- require concerted action at the EU level under the Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014 (IAS Regulation). The IAS Regulation list of Union concern currently includes 114 species (65 animals and 49 plants). A well-known example of IAS of EU concern is *Vespa velutina nigrithorax*, other species already regulated under separate frameworks could be

regarded IAS, for example the Japanese beetle (*Popillia japonica*) which is listed as a priority pest in the phytosanitary regime.

Globalisation- through transport, trade and tourism- is the principal driver of species movements. Once introduced, IAS can thrive and spread because of favourable climatic conditions, the absence of enemies and other facilitating processes. The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) classifies pathways of introduction as follows: intentional release in nature (e.g. introduction of biocontrol agents); escape from confinement (e.g. ornamental species); transport-stowaway/contaminant (e.g. hitching on vehicles and machinery); corridors (e.g. tunnels, bridges, waterways). Targeting high-risk pathways such as horticultural escape and contaminated commodities enables the EU to reduce propagule pressure, meet biodiversity targets, and strengthen early-detection and eradication programmes. This, in turn, mitigates ecological, economic and health impacts.

In a recent study (Rosace *et al.*, 2023), a dataset of plant pests first recorded in the EU between 1999 and 2019 was compiled within the context of the EU plant health framework. The European Alien Species Information Network (EASIN) was one of the data sources used. Of the 3,729 species listed in EASIN, 236 pests were retained for analysis, 146 of which originated exclusively from the EASIN source. A subsequent review by Magliozzi *et al.* (2025) examined the positive and negative impacts by 602 IAS in the EU, revealing partial overlaps, data discontinuities and a need for improved coordination among the 25 policy sectors for improving biological invasions management.

One illustrative case is *Buddleja davidii*. After being prioritised through horizon-scanning activities, the species would undergo risk-assessment and, if appropriate, inclusion on the Union list of concern. *B. davidii* entered the EU via the “escape from confinement: horticulture and ornamental use (other than horticulture)” pathway and has been shown to negatively affect the conservation status and trends of native species and habitats; impair infrastructure, exemplified by its invasion of approximately 61% of Belgian quarries (Monty *et al.*, 2019).

Management processes should consider the risks each IAS possess across all relevant policy sectors. Consistent EU-wide policy, shared data platforms and trans-border collaboration are essential to prevent, detect and manage invasive alien species effectively, thereby aligning legal obligations with practical, coordinated action.

Keywords: invasive alien species, pathways of introduction, EASIN, Cross sectoral coordination

References:

European Commission. (2026). EASIN - European Alien Species Information Network. *EASIN*. <https://easin.jrc.ec.europa.eu/easin>

Magliozzi, C., Cardoso, A. C., Gervasini, E., Melone, B., Bizzotto, E. C., Brundu, G., Cagnacci, F., Cebrian, E., Adriaens, T., Alves, M. H., Bartilotti, C., Carnevali, L., Duarte, S., Groom, Q., Queiroga, R. M., Meeus, S., Nunes, A. L., Preda, C., Rendón-Hernández, E., Vanden Abeele, S., Scalera, R., Vanhove, M. & Álvaro, N. V. (2025). Aligning EU policies to address biological invasions: Assessing invasion impacts across sectors. *NeoBiota*, 102, 295–312. <https://doi.org/10.3897/neobiota.102.152015>

Monty, A., Jorion, A., Pitz, C., Géron, C. & Mahy, G. (2019). Alien invasive plants in Belgian limestone quarries. *BASE*, 23(3), 160–164. <https://popups.uliege.be/1780-4507/index.php?id=17984>

Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 October 2014 on the Prevention and Management of the Introduction and Spread of Invasive Alien Species, OJ L 317 35 (2014). <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2014/1143/2019-12-14>

Rosace, M. C., Cendoya, M., Mattion, G., Vicent, A., Battisti, A., Cavaletto, G., Marini, L. & Rossi, V. (2023). A spatio-temporal dataset of plant pests' first introductions across the EU and potential entry pathways. *Sci Data*, 10, 731. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02643-9>

Maria Luisa Paracchini D.6. - Nature Conservation and Observations

Topic: Main risk drivers affecting ecosystem condition

Summary: 2nd Mapping and assessing of EU Ecosystems and their Services is currently under writing. The second edition of MAES is planned for publication by early 2027. The update of the first edition of the report, so called MAES1 (Maes *et al.*, 2020) was initiated in 2025 (Paracchini *et al.*, 2026). It will contribute to the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 while providing information to the IPBES Second Global Assessment of 2028 and concurring to the Global Biodiversity Framework. The report is organised by ecosystem type, for which pressures and condition indicator trends are provided. An overview about MAES1 conclusions for each ecosystem type is provided, together with some preliminary views on MAES2 updates. In urban ecosystems, for instance, most of trends observed in MAES1 show improvements in air pollutant emissions. Condition indicator trends for forest ecosystems show mostly stable or worsening values. A detailed study (Maes *et al.*, 2023) showed that though forest condition overall marked a slight improvement between 2000 and 2018, one third of the forest area was subject to declining condition. In all ecosystems, the driver of climate change shows a general downward trend. Conclusions on soil ecosystems converge with outcomes by EUSO (online), where more than half of soils are at degraded state, reaching the 62% in agricultural areas. An important aspect is that evidence seems to indicate that policies have positive effects in improving ecosystems condition.

Other activities performed by the JRC within this framework include i) Natural Capital Accounting (INCA platform) with quantification of stocks and flows of ecosystem services ii) indicator B1 of the Global Biodiversity Framework, that shows a positive trend for cultural services, stable for provisioning services and negative for regulating and maintenance services over the period 2006-2018.

The accounting of unmet demand for ecosystem services is a useful analysis to identify those services from which the society cannot benefit, that in case of EU are particularly evident for regulating and maintenance services (e.g. air filtration, water purification).

Keywords: climate change, ecosystem services, pressures, drivers, natural capital accounting.

References:

European Commission. (2026a). EUSO Soil Degradation Dashboard. *EUSO (EU Soil Observatory)*. <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/esdacviewer/euso-dashboard/>

European Commission. (2026b). INCA Platform. *INCA (Integrated System for Natural Capital Accounting)*. <https://ecosystem-accounts.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

Maes, J., Bruzón, A. G., Barredo, J. I., Vallecillo, S., Vogt, P., Rivero, I. M. & Santos-Martín, F. (2023). Accounting for forest condition in Europe based on an international statistical standard. *Nature Communications*, 14, 3723. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-39434-0>

Maes, J., Teller, A., Erhard, M., Conde, S., Vallecillo Rodriguez, S., Barredo Cano, J.I., Paracchini, M.-L., Abdul Malak, D., Trombetti, M., Vigiak, O., Zulian, G., Addamo, A., Grizzetti, B., Somma, F., Hagyo, A., Vogt, P., Polce, C., Jones, A., Marin, A., Ivits, E., Mauri, A., Rega, C., Czucz, B., Ceccherini, G., Pisoni, E., Ceglar, A., De Palma, P., Cerrani, I., Meroni, M., Caudullo, G., Lugato, E., Vogt, J., Spinoni, J., Cammalleri, C., Bastrup-Birk, A., San-Miguel-Ayanz, J., San Román, S., Kristensen, P., Christiansen, T., Zal, N., De Roo, A., De Jesus Cardoso, A., Pistocchi, A., Del Barrio Alvarellos, I., Tsiamis, K., Gervasini, E., Deriu, I., La Notte, A., Abad Viñas, R., Vizzarri, M., Camia, A., Robert, N., Kakoulaki, G., Garcia Bendito, E., Panagos, P., Ballabio, C., Scarpa, S., Montanarella, L., Orgiazzi, A., Fernandez Ugalde, O. & Santos-Martín, F. (2020). Mapping and assessment of ecosystems and their services: An EU wide ecosystem assessment in support of the EU biodiversity strategy. *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/757183>

European Commission. Joint Research Centre, Paracchini, M. L., Vallecillo, S., Marchetti, A., Marcantonio, M., Barredo, J. I., Sánchez-Espinosa, A., Trombetti, M., Galimberti, F., Alonso Aller, E., Arias Navarro, C., Cardoso, A. C., Grammatikopoulou, I., Czúcz, B., Abdul Malak, D., Cadahía Lorenzo, L., Caudullo, G., Grizzetti, B., Guerrero Fernandez, I., Jones, A., Kolstad, A., Kuželová, K., La Notte, A., Liakos, L., Liqueste, C., Malek, Z., Magliozzi, C., Nocita, M., Orgiazzi, A., Pardo, A., Petersen, J.E., Piroddi, C., Pisani, D., Polce, C., Scarpa, S., Van Der Velde, M., Vighi, M., Weiss, M., Zulian, G. & Zurbaran Nucci, M. (2026). Towards the second EU Ecosystem Assessment. *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2760/1394895>

Adamantia Athanasopoulou E.3. Built Environment

Topic: Risks in the built environment

Summary: The built environment refers to different human-made constructions such as buildings (residential, commercial, industrial), transport infrastructures (roads, bridges, railways, etc), public spaces (parks, plazas, etc), utility networks (systems for water, electricity, gas, telecommunications). The built environment is part of our daily life and is vulnerable to natural and human-made hazards, aggravated by the impact of climate change (EEA, 2024), ageing assets and the availability of raw materials for its construction. Besides risks faced by buildings, bridges and tunnels in the Trans-European Transport network (TEN-T) present structural deficiencies, were designed in some cases with older and outdated standards and are reaching, in many places, the end of their lifetime. Further, the TEN-T network overlaps with more than 90% with the military networks of the EU MSs, making the TEN-T bridges and tunnels assets of

dual use. Therefore, risks connected to military mobility and needs should be taken into account. Looking into more detail in risks faced in the built environment, there are geophysical risks, most notably earthquakes, especially in southern EU. Earthquakes is the deadliest disaster in the world and the second most expensive after floods in Europe. Other geophysical risks of concern include landslides, soil liquefaction, landslides and subsequent debris flow. Climatic stressors (wind, snow, rainfall, ice, extreme temperatures) and environmental hazards (soil erosion, corrosion, material degradation) can also affect the built environment. Human-made hazards and stressors, such as fires, intentional actions (explosions), lack of maintenance (due to restricted budget, and/or uncertainty on when to intervene or how) represent another substantial source of risk. Many risks in the built environment are not new but are exacerbated by climate change and aging asset. The current concerns are how to adapt the design of built infrastructure and their monitoring to face climate change (Polo Lopez *et al.*, 2025). Combined or sequential risks can further threaten the resilience of the built environment. For example, the natural corrosion of steel in reinforced concrete structures can be accelerated due to climate change (Dimova *et al.*, 2024). There are also unknown factors, like the effect of vegetation in expanding cities where the interface between the built environment and natural environment increases consistently. What are the effects of cascading hazards and multiple hazards, how to approach them – think for example wildfires in the wildland-urban interface, should we re-consider the design standards for buildings found in wildfire prone areas (Sciarretta *et al.*, 2025)? Another example of multiple hazards was encountered during the Covid confinement, where an earthquake occurred and the evacuation protocol was clashing with the social distancing.

Keywords: built environment, climate change, combined risks.

References:

European Commission. (2026). Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T). https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/infrastructure-and-investment/trans-european-transport-network-ten-t_en

European Commission. Joint Research Centre, Dimova, S., Polo López, C. S., Sousa, M. L., Rianna, G., Bastidas-Arteaga, E., Nogal, M., Gervásio, H., Martorana, E., Reder, A. & Athanasopoulou, A. (2024). Impact of climate change on the corrosion of the European reinforced concrete building stock. (S. Dimova, C. S. Polo López, M. L. Sousa, Eds). *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/016004>

European Environment Agency. (2024). European climate risk assessment. (No. 01/2024). *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://doi.org/10.2800/8671471>

Polo López, C. S., Tsionis, G., Athanasopoulou, A., Sciarretta, F., Reder, A., Rianna, G., Dosio, A., Cagnazzo, C., Formichi, P., Croce, P., andi, F., Nogal Macho, M., Dimova, S., Sousa, M. L., Catarino, J. M., Oliveira Santos, L., Deus, R., Cabrinha, V., Wichura, B. & Castino, F. (2025). Climate change adaptation for the built environment: Developments and needs for structural design standards. (G. Tsionis, C. S. Polo López, European Commission, & Joint Research Centre, Eds). *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/3620533>

European Commission. Joint Research Centre, Sciarretta, F., Athanasopoulou, A., Polo Lopez, C., Tsionis, G., Debrouwere, B., Jönsson, J., Joyeux, D., Kotsovinos, P., Manzello, S. L., Merci, B., Nogal-Macho, M., Okwara, F., Poulsen, A., Rios, O., Samaras, P., Tondini, N., van Hees, P. & Węgrzyński, W. (2025). Prospects for implementation of fire safety engineering approach in

Europe (F. Sciarretta, A. Athanasopoulou, & G. Tsionis, Eds). *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/1335237>

Karmen Poljansek E.1. - Disaster Risk Management

Topic: The INFORM Framework for Risk Drivers of Humanitarian crisis

Summary: INFORM is a multi-stakeholder forum for developing shared, quantitative, analytical products related to humanitarian crises and disasters. Driven by escalating global instability, the humanitarian landscape is deteriorating at an alarming rate. By early 2025, nearly 425 million people will require assistance—a figure that has almost doubled since 2020. The INFORM initiative was established more than 10 years ago as direct response to this trajectory, leveraging science to shift the international community from reactive aid to a proactive, anticipatory mindset. INFORM is a suite of analytical tools designed to support decision making in different stages of disaster risk management cycle:

- INFORM Risk provides a risk score for every country for prevention.
- INFORM Warning monitors early signals for anticipatory actions.
- INFORM Severity measures the severity of ongoing crises to support immediate response to crisis.
- INFORM Climate Change quantifies future risks of humanitarian crisis for long-term adaptations.

Disaster Risk Management (DRM) is the operational application of disaster risk reduction strategies targeting risk drivers throughout the entire DRM cycle. Because risks of varying origins require tailored actions, affecting specific drivers in different DRM phases. This understanding enables a seamless transition from proactive prevention and preparedness to reactive response, effectively reducing risk to an acceptable level. Similarly, within the humanitarian community, the combination of anticipatory and response measures is essential to harmonizing humanitarian and developmental approaches.

To manage crises effectively, risk and impact must not be confused: Impact belongs to the past, representing tangible historical losses, while Risk belongs to the future, representing potential impact. Disaster Risk is an assessment of this future potential. It is calculated through specific risk drivers and validated by historical impact data, while always accounting for inherent levels of uncertainty. By identifying risk as potential impact, we can act before the "potential" becomes a "reality". The current concept of risk is defined by the interplay of three dimensions: hazard and exposure, vulnerability, and lack of coping capacity. These dimensions are quantified through more than 80 distinct indicators to form the INFORM Risk Index. Since 2014, this index has served as the global reference for multi-hazard risk assessment. It specifically measures the risk of humanitarian crises that will exceed a nation's capacity to respond within a three-to-five-year time horizon.

The global risk landscape is changing, characterized by a dangerous reality of fluid transitions and overlaps between ongoing crises and new disasters. Using comparable metrics of three core INFORM products (Risk, Severity, and Climate Change) INFORM maps countries risk trajectories

across a temporal spectrum: a 10-year retrospective risk view, the current landscape of risk and active humanitarian crises to future climate projections. While climate change is already intensifying hazards and shortening recovery windows, we have not yet seen the true, full impact to validate the assessment. Consequently, we cannot present a single result anymore, but rather scenario combinations for different futures.

This data brings us to a critical realization: the scenario that eventually evolves depends entirely on our strategic decisions today. This forces us to move beyond traditional, data-driven models, which reach their limit with unprecedented risks, and enter the realm of Strategic Foresight. To achieve true anticipation, we must systematically challenge the assumptions that constrain our vision and explore a range of plausible, unseen futures.

Ultimately, our work in understanding risk drivers and the global landscape is not about fear; it is about building a Strategic Foundation. This knowledge provides the essential baseline needed to move from a data-driven past to a foresight-driven future.

Keywords: foresight, unprecedented futures, global risks, humanitarian crisis, risk drivers, INFORM

References:

European Commission. (2026). INFORM - Global, open-source risk assessment for humanitarian crises and disasters. *DRMKC - INFORM*. <https://drmkc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/inform-index>

Danila Volpi E.1. - Disaster Risk Management

Topic: Drought risk for vegetation and crop

Summary: Drought is defined as a period of unusually and persistently dry conditions that alters the hydrological balance. The Copernicus Emergency Management Service provides two platforms for drought monitoring: European and Global drought observatories.

Droughts can be classified into three classes: meteorological drought with a deficit of precipitation, agricultural drought with a deficit of soil water and a water stress for vegetation, and hydrological drought with a reduction of stream and reservoir stream flow. Agricultural drought is monitored with the Combined Drought Indicator (CDI). The data gathered is from 2012 and up to date and the spatial resolution in Europe is 5km. The CDI (Sepulcre-Canto *et al.*, 2012) is calculated every 10 days, because a water stress lasting at least 10-20 days can have severe effect over vegetation and crop production. The CDI integrates the SPI (Standardized Precipitation Index), the SMA (Soil Moisture Anomaly) and the FAPAR (Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation). The FAPAR is used as a proxy to vegetation health because water stress reduces plant capacity to intercept solar radiation. A negative FAPAR could therefore indicate the presence of drought (Cammalleri *et al.*, 2022), but also other factors such as plant diseases or absence of vegetation, e.g. after harvest. It is to account for these biases unrelated to water stress that the FAPAR is combined with SPI and the SMA to calculate the CDI.

The EDORA project (Enhancing DrOught Resilience and Adaptation) is a multi-sectoral impact assessment to estimate the drought related risks in the present and future. Many sectors are covered by this study, among which rain fed and irrigated agriculture, and terrestrial ecosystems.

The risk assessment process is composed by two steps: i) conceptual models, to explore drought drivers for the different sectors through impact chains, ii) data-driven analysis, based on machine learning models trained to know the relationship between impact and drought hazards to identify the better suited indices to use. The drought risk is then estimated as an average annual loss: the main outcome of EDORA is EDRA (European Drought Risk Atlas). The atlas is accessible as an interactive map where the average annual loss can be visualized across Europe for each sector, comparing different warming level projections. EDID (European Drought impact Database) is another EDORA outcome, providing over 13.000 georeferenced records of drought impacts in Europe across different sectors and covering a timeframe from 1970 to present, to support impact-based assessments. Various sources are used, mainly media news and government authorities, but also direct observations and scientific literature. The records are available on a map and through a search database; they all contain georeferenced data, drought severity, time stamp, short description and reference. Currently, the goal for EDID is to keep the database up to date and automate the data collection.

Keywords: drought, impact assessment, precipitations, warming

References:

Cammalleri, C., McCormick & N., Toreti, A. (2022). Analysis of the relationship between yield in cereals and remotely sensed fAPAR in the framework of monitoring drought impacts in Europe. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 22, 3737–3750. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-22-3737-2022>

Copernicus - European Commission. (2026a). Drought Observatories of the Copernicus Emergency Management Service. *The European and Global Drought Observatories*. <https://drought.emergency.copernicus.eu/>

Copernicus - European Commission. (2026b). European Drought Impact Database (EDID). *European Drought Impact Database*. <https://drought.emergency.copernicus.eu/impacts/#/home>

Copernicus - European Commission. (2026c). European Drought Risk Atlas (EDRA). *The European and Global Drought Observatories*. <https://drought.emergency.copernicus.eu/tumbo/edra>

Cammalleri, C., McCormick, N., Toreti, A. (2022). Analysis of the relationship between yield in cereals and remotely sensed fAPAR in the framework of monitoring drought impacts in Europe. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 22(11), 3737–3750. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-22-3737-2022>

Luigi Spagnolo E1 – Disaster Risk Management

Topic: Building ontologies for crisis management: insights for plant health

Summary: Ontologies can be defined as a formal representation of knowledge within a specific domain. ‘Formal’ refers to the use of a structured and precise language that follows precise syntactic and semantic rules, allowing computers to process information consistently, and deliver unambiguous interpretations. The knowledge represented in this way includes collected facts, concepts and relationships, and may cover one or multiple domains according to scope and context of the ontology.

Drivers are anomalous phenomena that increase the magnitude of a hazard, the exposure to it, the vulnerability of affected systems, and/or that trigger other hazards. Signals are specific manifestations of drivers and may therefore indicate the emergence of more severe events.

The ongoing project is carried out in collaboration with ontology experts from the Italian National Research Council and the University of Mannheim. Its objective is to define multiple ontologies and/or link them to existing standards, establishing core concepts and relationships that are shared across sectors, with public health as the first priority. A whole-of-government, cross-sectoral approach can facilitate harmonisation, improve semantic interoperability, and support data integration and analysis, particularly when applying AI technologies. To foster this development there is the need of support of exchanging data across systems by exposing web APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) in standard formats that help to investigate solutions for ontology curation and governance. This cooperation is organised into four interconnected levels: legislative, organisational, semantic and technical interoperability. Semantic interoperability refers to the ability to exchange and integrate data using common metadata, reference models, and systems.

Building a common semantic framework requires defining both actual (or forecasted) events and potential risk scenarios – i.e. hypothetical manifestations of hazards – while capturing the actual/possible evolution of situations, and modelling the interrelationships, including cascading effects. A key challenge is dealing with ambiguities as differences in predictability, context, impact severity and urgency may lead to discrepant interpretations of terms, such as crisis, threat, or emergency.

Two potential solutions are being explored:

- i) Abstract representations based on Petri nets, where states and transitions characterise events and risk scenarios, allowing the modelling of relationships and cascading hazards.
- ii) Inference of event types from their associated hazards, status (reported, forecasted, etc.) and other available features, such as severity. This allows the establishment of formal rules that define concepts, such as incident or emergency, reducing ambiguity.

This project can support HS in plant health, by providing a more comprehensive classification and representation of knowledge to aid signal detection. Relationships between concepts can guide the refinement and prioritisation of signals to be identified (e.g. symptoms or environmental factors identifying specific pests) and enhance interaction with other HS communities (e.g. on One Health surveillance).

As an illustrative example, the pest *Phakopsora cherimoliae* is used to model a single event (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Example of a conceptual ontology model for an event regarding the first finding (outbreak) of the pest *Phakopsora cherimoliae* in China

The ontology describing this event (i.e., *P. cherimoliae* -> new host for infectious agent -> biological event -> hazardous event) is linked to related ontologies describing hazards (e.g., pest, fungus, infectious agent, biological hazard) and exposure (e.g., country, plant). These elements can then be associated with relevant risk drivers (e.g., environmental degradation) and signals (e.g., severe rust disease).

Keywords: communication, ontologies, taxonomy, interoperability

References:

Huang, Q., Wan, J., Li, X., Zhao, S., Liu, G., Li, Y. & Xiao, S. (2025). First report of *Phakopsora cherimoliae* causing rust disease on *Annona squamosa* in China. *Plant Disease*, 109(11), 2429. <https://doi.org/10.1094/PDIS-04-25-0817-PDN>

Francesca Torti T.5 – Data Intelligence for Policy

Topic: An Overview of International Trade Monitoring by JRC

Summary: The Unit T.5 belongs to the Digital Transformation, AI and Data Directorate of the JRC. There, the Data Analysis and Robust Statistics (DARS) team is responsible for the development and implementation of innovative statistical research and analysis for international trade, Customs Union, anti-fraud, and taxation policies, with a focus on identifying and mitigating financial risk. This is done performing statistical estimates, robust to anomalies and deviations from model assumptions, in different contexts such as: linear regression, time series, categorical

data (e.g., correspondence analysis and co-clustering), clustering. The Flexible Statistics for Data Analysis (FSDA) toolbox is an open-source robust statistical library created on MATLAB to support this type of analysis as a joint project between the University of Parma and the JRC.

The international trade data analysed by DARS come from:

- TAXUD-Surveillance: enables to follow in real time transactions at single consignment level between EU and extra-EU countries. This means that it captures only trade flows into and out of the EU, but not between EU MSs (e.g. flows from France to Spain) and not between third countries (e.g. exports from US to China). The three main variables are traded i) value, ii) weight and iii) units, and goods are identified according to TARIC classification (10 digits). The utilization of real time data allows for daily updates, although errors may be detected with delay and can alter the recordings in retrospect.
- ESTAT-ComExt: is the Eurostat database for trade statistics and flows of the European Union both with extra-EU countries and between MSs. Data are provided at aggregated level, and according to CN classification (8 digits). The accessibility of data can be delayed up to three months.
- UN-COMTRADE and Trade Data Monitoring (TDM) are official repositories of worldwide trade data, aggregated according to HS classification (6 digits).

The analysis performed by DARS of international trade data supports two main EU policies:

- Anti-fraud: by i) estimation of EU prices, ii) detection of under- and over-invoicing, iii) detection of trade deflection to evade sanctions.
- Competitiveness: by detection of dumping.

A practical example on the analysis of EU prices for asparagus from Peru developed in support to EFSA pest risk assessment activities is provided: under this activity it was possible to identify repeated under invoicing by certain countries. Other practical examples of outcomes of DARS analysis were shared and available on the presentation slides.

Keywords: robust statistics, international trade data, anti-fraud, dumping

References:

EUROSTAT, European Commission. COMEXT. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/international-trade-in-goods/database>

TAXUD, European Commission. (2026). Surveillance system. *Taxation and Customs Union*. https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/online-services/online-services-and-databases-customs/surveillance-system_en

LLC. (2026). About Trade Data Monitor. *Trade Data Monitor*. <https://tradedatamonitor.com/>

Robust Statistics Academy (Ro. S. A.) (2017). FSDA (Flexible Statistics for Data Analysis) Toolbox «Ro.S.A.». *Robust Statistics Academy (Ro. S. A.) - University of Parma*. <https://rosa.unipr.it/fsda.html>

United Nations. (2025). UN Comtrade Database. <https://comtradeplus.un.org/>

Lydia Caldana S.1 – Competence Centre on Foresight

Topic: Competence Centre of Foresight of the European Commission

Summary: The JRC EU Policy Lab provides a framework to strengthen EU policymaking competences, working in collaboration with key actors such as the European Strategy and Policy Analysis System (ESPAS), the Inter-Institutional Foresight Network. One of the Lab's guiding approaches is the "Be Futures Literate" framework, which promotes an anticipatory mindset, by encouraging the ability to scan, understand and influence change (JRC, 2025a). Given the exponential speed of global changes, greater preparedness is required to take informed action today in order to prepare for the future.

Current challenges for policymakers include identifying effective policy options, adopting a system perspective, managing continuous changes and being adaptive. The EU Policy Lab supports this by creating a collaborative and experimental space, that integrates **foresight, behavioural insights** and **design**.

Foresight is defined as a structured, systematic and systemic approach aimed at gaining valuable insights about the mid/long-term future. It helps clarify scenarios and megatrends. Various methods can be used to spot, understand and influence change, including Delphi, futures wheel, scenario building, priority road mapping, wind tunnelling, stress testing, reference foresight scenarios and HS. HS consists of a systematic examination of potential threats, opportunities and early signs of future developments located at the margins of current thinking and planning. Its focus is not on risks already occurring but on new potential threats. Each cycle involves collecting signals, synthesising the information, and projecting possible future impacts. The HS newsletter, published 3 times per year, presents the outcomes of each scanning cycle and typically highlights around 20 emerging issues.

Regarding **behavioural insights**, some megatrends identified for 2040 include: deceptive calm, sustainability paradigm, digital champions and turbulent times. Another key tool is the Megatrends Hub, an online repository that organises foresight-related information around 14 global megatrends (JRC, 2025b).

All EU-Learn tools and workshops are available to EU institutions, agencies and bodies. Additional resources at EU level include Futures for Europe (Futures4Europe, online), the open platform of the European Foresight Community, set-up by RTD and JRC, hosted by Eye for Europe.

The JRC also supports the Secretariat-General in producing the annual Strategic Foresight Report (European Commission, 2025), the EU's flagship foresight product. This report informs policy priorities and long-term strategic thinking on cross-cutting themes. The previous edition focused on resilience, whereas the current one addresses geopolitical tensions.

From the **design** perspective, the Water Resilience Project aims to envision possible futures for centralised and decentralised water-reuse systems, helping anticipate societal and systemic barriers to water-reuse uptake, and informing ongoing and future policy work (JRC, 2025c). A last example is the Intergenerational Fairness Strategy project (DG COMM, online), which aims to strengthen communication across generations and ensure that the interests of both present and future generations are reflected throughout the EU policymaking and legislation. This is a cross-cutting project spanning the entire Design-Foresight-AI ecosystem, led by the EU Policy Lab. Its outputs will be delivered by April 2026.

Keywords: foresight, megatrends, scenarios.

References:

Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council - 2025 Strategic Foresight Report - Resilience 2.0: Empowering the EU to Thrive amid Turbulence and Uncertainty, COM/2025/484 final (2025). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52025DC0484>

European Commission. (2023). Competence framework for 'innovative policymaking'. Knowledge for Policy. https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/visualisation/competence-framework-innovative-policymaking_en

European Commission. (2025a). Competence frameworks for policymakers and researchers. Knowledge for Policy. https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/projects-activities/competence-frameworks-policymakers-researchers_en

European Commission. (2025b). (De)centralized water reuse. Knowledge for Policy. https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/projects-activities/decentralized-water-reuse_en

European Commission. (2025c). Intergenerational Fairness. Citizens' Engagement Platform. https://citizens.ec.europa.eu/concluded-online-debates/intergenerational-fairness_en

European Commission. (2025d). The Megatrends Hub. Knowledge for Policy. https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/foresight/tool/megatrends-hub_en

Futures4Europe—The online home of the European foresight community. (2025). <https://www.futures4europe.eu/>

Participants' presentations:

James Cullum – CABI / Lead Content Analyst

Topic: CABI data, horizon scanning and risk monitoring

Summary: CABI is a non-profit organisation owned by 48 member countries, addressing global challenges such as food security through research and international development cooperation (CABI, 2026a). It is also a major publisher of scientific information, providing publications and a wide range of online resources (CABI, 2026b). For example, the CABI Compendium contains 80,000 datasheets on species, pests and diseases relevant to agriculture and the environment. These datasheets include information on distribution, taxonomy, habitat, pathways, risk and impact factors, and are interconnected through a semantic database that enables navigation between hosts and pests.

CABI also provides decision-support tools, such as:

- Horizon Scanning tool: it allows users to prioritise invasive species threats to an “area at risk” based on source regions, trade and transport routes, climate matching (using current climatic zones or projections for the 2050s). The tool is powered by CABI Compendium data and can perform scans by pathways, hosts, habitats, expected impacts or organism types.
- Pest Risk Analysis Tool: it supports structured assessment of pest-related risks associated with a proposed plant commodity pathway, multiple pathways for an individual pest, or an intentional introduction.
- Invasive Species Discovery tool: it enables users to generate invasive species lists based on habitat, pathways, risk and impact factors.

CABI Thesaurus is a knowledge graph, forming the semantic backbone of the CABI Compendium and related tools. Aligned with GBIF taxonomy standards and the CBD (Convention on Biological Diversity) pathway schema, it links species to their synonyms, taxonomic hierarchy, associated environments, positive and negative interactions, spread mechanisms, impact factors, symptoms, and external databases such as GBIF.

As a part of the PlantwisePlus programme, CABI assists NPPOs and RPPOs (national and regional plant protection organisations) in Africa and Asia with the development and maintenance of Pest Risk Registers (CABI, 2026c). This capacity building approach aims to ensure that Pest Risk Registers are maintained beyond programme’s conclusion. Simultaneously, Pest Risk Monitoring reports are generated using EIOS outputs, tailored to the NPPOs’ needs indicated in their Pest Risk Registers. To generate these reports, articles related to the listed pest sourced from EIOS are transferred into a dedicated CABI database. A machine-learning model then evaluates the articles, selecting those that are suitable for inclusion in the reports. Experts review these recommendations, either validating or rejecting them; their feedback is used to refine the model’s accuracy. The final reports are distributed to NPPOs to help them update their Pest Risk Registers and identify any necessary follow-on actions.

Future improvements include expanding the Pest Risk Register and Pest Risk Monitoring reports offering to more countries, further enhancing and updating CABI Compendium data, and enhancing trade-related information and climate-matching features within the HS tool.

Keywords: climate matching, model performance, pest risk register, taxonomy.

References:

- CABI. (2026a). CABI. <https://www.cabi.org/>
- CABI. (2026b). CABI Digital Library. *CABI Digital Library*. <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/>
- CABI. (2026c). PlantwisePlus. *CABI*. <https://www.cabi.org/plantwiseplus/>
- GBIF: The Global Biodiversity Information Facility. (2026). <https://www.gbif.org/>
- Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity (SCBD). (2026). Convention on Biological Diversity. *Convention on Biological Diversity*. <https://www.cbd.int/>

Gianfranco Spiteri – ECDC / Head of Section Global Epidemic Intelligence and Health Security

Topic: Threat detection at Epidemic Intelligence activities at the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC)

Summary: The ECDC activities are related on the early identification, verification, assessment and investigation of potential threats to human health in order to recommend public health measures to control them. It focuses on any risk to EU citizens posed by communicable diseases originating within the EU or globally. Unlike other ECDC units which are disease-focused, the Global Epidemic Intelligence and Health Security uses a broad, non-specific approach. Experts work 24/7 to respond quickly to acute events The process consists of an early detection phase (screening of information in EIOS system, filtering according to its relevance and validating using official sources) and final documentation phase (analysing and further actions).

The sources under screening are indicator-based, such as database surveys (lists of cases reported directly to ECDC) and web-scraping; and event-based, including outbreaks reported by MSs and opensource data from EIOS or social media. This monitoring activity can be either non-specific or target global threats like cholera, measles, or dengue. To perform this task, two experts monitor EIOS multiple times a day by gathering the information into different thematics: long-term-monitored threats, acute events, early warning screening, or mass gathering events. The screening of events-based data allows an enhanced monitoring, for example, specific web feeds were created to cover the Paris Olympics and natural disasters like earthquakes, as these events could spread communicable diseases.

All surveillance activities are part of ECDC detection efforts, which connect closely to response action. Expert roundtables are held regularly to assess information, with integration of inputs from disease-specific teams. Together, they determine the appropriate ECDC response. Most events are acute and occur quickly, but natural disasters require ongoing monitoring to anticipate cascading risks that could lead to disease outbreaks. ECDC uses a range of tools for surveillance: indicator-based (EpiPulse cases, where data about outbreaks from MSs is gathered; web scraping), event-based (restricted platforms and official public sources from national and international websites) and media monitoring (EIOS, other media aggregators, social media platforms). In 2021 EpiPulse online portal was launched to integrate the different surveillance platforms (The European Surveillance System (Tessy), the five Epidemic Intelligence Information System (EPIS) platforms and the Threat Tracking Tool (TTT) (ECDC, 2021). EpiPulse contains components (developed or in progress) for report production and publication. The Global

Epidemic Intelligence and Health Security team is working to link EIOS to the EpiPulse portal, such as integration of EIOS AI tool to transcribe videos and images into text, an R Shiny app that links mass gathering data from EIOS into EpiPulse Events, and an application for automatically collecting open-source data. Since EIOS collects data from open sources, it could help contextualise information about ongoing events. Data is usually collected more frequently than communicable; however, the team is collaborating with JRC to implement this linkage manually, with plans to automate it later.

The Global Epidemic Intelligence and Health Security team produces daily and weekly restricted reports for internal ECDC use. Weekly public reports are published on the ECDC website, summarising currently monitored events (ECDC, 2026a). For threats identified to pose a higher risk, epidemiological updates are produced as formal risk assessments (ECDC 2026b). For the future, ECDC plans to automate the publishing process and refine high-risk assessment procedures to help scientists and experts perform literature reviews within very short timelines (1-2 days) to gather and summarise all evidence related to a disease.

Finally, ECDC is building a network with the MSs and their experts to train them, build capacity and disseminate information faster, for example by offering webinars on ongoing events for MSs.

Keywords: EpiPulse, event-based, reporting, human health

References:

ECDC. (2022). Weekly threats reports (CDTR). *European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC)*. <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-and-data/monitoring/weekly-threats-reports>

ECDC. (2026). EpiPulse—The European surveillance portal for infectious diseases. *European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC)*. <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/epipulse-european-surveillance-portal-infectious-diseases>

European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC). (2026). Assessment. *European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control*. <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/search?s=&f%5B0%5D=categories%3A3066>

Bernard Bottex – EFSA / Team Leader of the KNOW unit

Topic: EFSA's Emerging risks analysis and horizon scanning process

Summary: Under EU General Food law (Regulation (EC) N° 178/2002 – Articles 23 & 34), EFSA must identify and characterise emerging risks related to the agency activities: food safety, plant health, animal health and environmental aspects related to these areas. The EFSA strategy 2027 (EFSA, 2021), expanded the scope to preparedness as well, to anticipate the future food and feed safety landscape and adapt EFSA's priorities according to the needs. The KNOW (Knowledge Innovation, Partnership Management) Unit was created in 2022 to improve EFSA's environment and HS and forecasting activities, by identifying signals of risks. In this mindset, JRC Tool for Innovation Monitoring (TIM) was used to identify emerging chemical risks, as proof of concept. As the subject was quite broad, few relevant signals were captured within a large background

noise. The same process was tested for identifying new food/feed sources and production techniques with a similar unsatisfying result, meaning weak signal identification works poorly on broad search terms but better on specific areas. Another approach was then tested: setting up a global collaborative network for preparedness, with representatives of EC, EU agencies, MSs and extra-EU competent authorities like USDA and Health Canada, international organisations such as the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and WHO. Another part of the network is the StaDG-ER (Stakeholder Discussion Group on Emerging Risks), composed of representatives from registered EFSA stakeholder groups (e.g. consumers, environmental/health NGOs and/or advocacy groups, farmers, industry, etc). In EFSA, the HS workflow starts by capturing signals, as previously described, that are not part of the current EFSA work programmes or the EFSA strategy. The next steps include the identification of potential EFSA's partners working already on the thematic, their partnering interest and availability, if EFSA has the capacity and knowledge to work on the topic or if it deserves the creation of an *ad hoc* pool of experts. Finally, EFSA management decides if the thematic should be added to its strategy and with what priority level. For each identified emerging risk, a note is written and stored in a central database.

As an example, plant health related emerging risks captured by the network can be specific plant pests or broader issues that may impact plant health. These signals are then shared with the EFSA Plant Health Monitoring team to assess the relevance.

Examples of signals captured in 2025 by this HS activity related to plant health are:

- Carbon offsetting: industrial activities producing CO₂ must compensate their emissions, for example by planting trees. But afforestation can also produce monocultures or introduce alien species and related plant pests to the EU if not properly managed.
- Agro-climatic zones shifting northward: warmer climate crops like maize will no longer be suitable in southern EU, and the shift of their cultivation north will force new regions to deal with new risks like mycotoxins, pesticide resistance and new plant pests.
- Agroterrorism and cyber-attacks on the food supply chain: is EU prepared to deal with voluntary introduction of plant pests that can damage agriculture and the food production system in members states? A multi-agency, multi-MS crisis exercise will be organised in 2026 on this topic to be better prepared for these events.

Currently the activity of signals identification is performed by EFSA staff, several EU projects are contributing to this activity. In particular Holifood, that uses AI and big data technologies for early warning, identification and emerging risk predictions of known and unknown food safety hazards.

EFSA also has foresight activities, trying to identify the options for EFSA future strategy that will start in 2028. One activity was imagining the future of food and feed safety landscape in 10 years and test the capacity to do this together with other EU agencies, the EC and JRC, in a One Health approach.

Keywords: emerging risk, one health, preparedness, signal

References:

European Food Safety Authority. (2025). EFSA strategy 2027: Science, safe food, sustainability: updated edition. *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://doi.org/10.2805/1198732>

Könnölä, T., Ferrari, A., Giesecke, S., Cuhls, K. & Banchs-Piqué, M. (2026). Multi-Agency Foresight with One Health Approach: Deliverable 5. *EFSA Supporting Publication*, 23(3), 91. <https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2026.EN-10045>

The use of AI for emerging food safety risk identification (interim HOLiFOOD results). (2025, June 18). *HOLiFOOD*. <https://holifoodproject.eu/the-use-of-ai-for-emerging-food-safety-risk-identification/>

Lucie Michel – Coordinator of the French Epidemiological Plant Health Surveillance Platform

Topic: The French national plant health surveillance platform

Summary: The French Epidemiological Plant Health Surveillance Platform (ESV Platform) is a collaborative, multidisciplinary and multi-stakeholder tool created in 2018. Governmental organisations as well as public and private research institutes are involved, to monitor generic and specific pests, covering both upstream (monitoring and prediction) and downstream (detection and response) approaches. ESV Platform is part of the national One Health system as it works alongside the national Animal Health Surveillance Platform (NAHSP) and Food Chain Surveillance Platform (SCA), sharing stakeholders, methodologies, and a shared governance to improve surveillance, risk assessment, and management of regulated plant pathogens. The goal of the ESV Platform is to improve the efficiency of plant health surveillance in France, enabling more effective pest control and prevention. This is achieved by strengthening the surveillance system, informing public policies and supporting epidemiological investigations. The Platform focuses on surveillance, while maintaining strong connections with research, reference laboratories, risk assessment and risk management activities. Its organisation is built around three core principles: consensus among the platform's participants, collaboration and interdisciplinarity among working groups, the three national surveillance platforms and the related scientific fields. Seven working groups address specific pests (e.g. *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*, *Candidatus Liberibacter asiaticus*, *Xylella fastidiosa*), or broader subjects such as epidemic intelligence. In addition, fast-reaction project teams are dedicated to targeted and urgent questions (e.g. the decline of olive trees in Corsica): they involve informaticians, statisticians, epidemiologists and communication officers from Avignon, Montpellier and Lyon.

The plant health monitoring operates at two levels: i) upstream, tools and approaches aim to identify potential emerging risks at the international level, design surveillance strategies to anticipate likely pest emergence, and promote early detection; ii) downstream, efforts focus on analysing and improving surveillance activities and quickly detecting new outbreaks. Finally, targeted communication activities help raise awareness of plant health issues among multiple stakeholders.

Epidemic intelligence represents an example of upstream generalist monitoring. The web-scraping tool collects around a thousand articles a week about a dozen pest species. These articles are then downloaded, the data extracted, translated, and classified and clustered using machine learning and language models. This activity delivers weekly and monthly bulletins summarizing the selected generic and specific news about plant health and are freely available online (distribution list, online).

An example of upstream, specific surveillance is the pinewood nematode (PWN) case. The first outbreak of *B. xylophilus* was recorded in France in November 2025, in the municipality of Seignosse, Landes department (EPPO, 2025). Already in 2023, the risk maps produced by the *B. xylophilus* working group identified the Landes department as a very high-risk area. The risk maps are used to propose risk-based monitoring plans, such as sampling plans for trapping: in the nematode's case, the Landes region was identified as needing more trapping than most of France.

In conclusion, the ESV Platform aims to strengthen plant health surveillance by acting as a bridge between public and private sectors and working closely with research organisations. To enhance its effectiveness, there is a growing need for improved epidemiological surveillance tools. Additionally, integrating risk-foresight approaches into both upstream and downstream

surveillance is essential to better anticipate emerging threats and detect outbreaks as early as possible. This will enable public authorities to implement appropriate surveillance and response measures in a timely manner.

Keywords: epidemiology, surveillance, timely reaction, web scrapping.

References:

EPPO. (2025). First report of *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* in France. *EPPO Global Database*. <https://gd.eppo.int/reporting/article-8278>

INRAE. (2026a). Bulletins et 'Points sur'. *Plateforme ESV*. https://plateforme-esv.fr/bulletins_et_points_sur_VSI

INRAE. (2026b). Plateforme d'Épidémiosurveillance en Santé Végétale. *Plateforme ESV*. <https://plateforme-esv.fr/>

INRAE. (2026c). Veille sanitaire internationale. *Plateforme ESV*. <https://plateforme-esv.fr/thematiques/GTVSI>

INRAE. (2026d). Groupe de travail *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*. *Plateforme ESV*. https://plateforme-esv.fr/thematiques/GTnematode_du_pin

Richard Mally – Forest Invasion Synthesis Centre from the Faculty of Forestry and Wood Sciences, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague - Entomologist

Topic: Macroecology and biogeography of global insect invasions.

Summary: The Forest Invasion Synthesis Centre studies biological invasions on a global level. As a synthesis centre, rather than generating data *per se*, it recycles data, retrieving it from all kinds of sources, and attempts to reanalyse it to find new answers to questions that could not be answered in the past (FISC, 2026a). Currently, efforts are made to bring together people from diverse backgrounds to gain a broader perspective on specific issues related to insect and other biological invasions.

There is an increasing number of biological invasions worldwide, predominantly driven by two groups: vascular plants and insects (Seebens *et al.*, 2017). For vascular plants, human assistance contributes directly to their propagation in the early stages of the invasion process, by facilitating ornamental and cultivated plants escaping their production areas where, in some cases, they become invasive. Based on the enemy release hypothesis, non-native plants have been benefiting from being introduced to new areas as the absence of their native enemies can facilitate their own growth in non-native regions. However, through global trade, natural enemies can catch up with their original hosts in the new regions, leading to demise or erosion of those hosts (Medzihorský *et al.*, 2024; Martin *et al.*, 2025).

To further assess invasion success, global insect diversity in the largest insect families (together around 900,000 species worldwide) was classified according to their larval feeding group (herbivores, detritivores incl. fungivores, predators, parasites, and brood cares) (Mally *et al.*, 2024). Herbivores were found significantly over-represented among non-natives compared to their proportion among insects, giving support to the idea that plant invasions facilitate insect

(and especially insect herbivore) invasions. Among non-native herbivores, the insect orders Hemiptera, Thysanoptera, Hymenoptera and Diptera were over-represented, and specific families could be identified that contribute most in these orders to invasion success (Mally *et al.*, 2025). Between the years 1700 and 2009, a substantial shift among feeding groups was observed, from primarily detritivores and predators in the 18th and early 19th century to predominantly herbivores from the mid-19th century on. This change could be related to changes in global invasion pathways, such as the shift from sailing ships carrying ballast that favoured soil-borne insects to faster steam- and motor ships, allowing transport of live plants and associated herbivores. Cross-correlation of invasion rates per decade of non-native plant and herbivore species indicated an 80-year lag between plant naturalisations and herbivore establishments, quantifying the average time that separates plant and insect herbivore invasions. Ongoing research (FISC, 2026b) is looking into the direct trophic connections between non-native plants and their herbivores by compiling a comprehensive dataset of native and non-native insect-plant associations for Europe.

Apart from the feeding group, the success of biological invasions might also have a strong phylogenetic component. Non-native species closely related to the species present in the invaded region might benefit from pre-adapted traits but might experience stronger competition with the natives; non-natives distantly related to the natives likely rely on different ecological niches, thus evading competition with the native species. By comparing insect genera shared among and unique to Europe, New Zealand and North America, we found evidence that non-native species in a genus that is present in the invaded region are more successful invaders, giving support to the hypothesis that assumes species closely related to the invaded species pool to be more successful invaders, termed "Darwin's pre-adaptation hypothesis" (Mally *et al.*, (under review)).

Keywords: biological invasions, native species, natural enemies, plant trade, trophic chain

References:

- FISC (2026a). Forest Invasion Synthesis Centre, Prague. FISC. <https://www.forestinvasion.cz/>
- FISC (2026b) Arka Pal, PhD student – Global synthesis of insect associations on non-native plants. FISC. <https://www.forestinvasion.cz/team/arka-pal/>
- Mally, R., Turner, R. M., Nahrung, H. F., Yamanaka, T., Fenn-Moltu, G., Bertelsmeier, C. & Liebhold, A. M. (2024). Historical invasion rates vary among insect trophic groups. *Current Biology*, 34(22), 5374-5381.e3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2024.09.068>
- Mally, R., Turner, R. M., Nahrung, H. F., Yamanaka, T., Fenn-Moltu, G., Bertelsmeier, C., Roques, A., Brockerhoff, E. G., Pureswaran, D. S. & Liebhold, A. M. (2025). Insect invasion success depends on taxon and trophic group. *NeoBiota*, 99, 19–43. <https://doi.org/10.3897/neobiota.99.151227>
- Seebens, H., Blackburn, T. M., Dyer, E. E., Genovesi, P., Hulme, P. E., Jeschke, J. M., Pagad, S., Pyšek, P., Winter, M., Arianoutsou, M., Bacher, S., Blasius, B., Brundu, G., Capinha, C., Celesti-Grapow, L., Dawson, W., Dullinger, S., Fuentes, N., Jäger, H., Kartesz, J., Kenis, M., Kreft, H., Kühn, I., Lenzner, B., Liebhold, A., Mosena, A., Moser, D. Nishino, M., Pearman, D., Pergl, J., Rabitsch, W., Rojas-Sandoval, J., Roques, A., Rorke, S., Rossinelli, S., Roy, H.E., Scalera R., Schindler, S., Štajerová, K., Tokarska-Guzik, B., van Kleunen, M., Walker, K., Weigelt, P. & Takehiko Yamanaka Essl, F. (2017). No saturation in the accumulation of alien species worldwide. *Nature Communications*, 8, 14435. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms14435>

Martin, G. D., Payne, S. L., Steenhuisen, S. L. & Mashamba, T. (2025). The demise of enemy release associated with the recruitment of natural enemies on an invasive tree. *Biological Invasions*, 27(10), 224. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-025-03681-7>

Medzihorský, V., Mally, R., Trombik, J., Turčáni, M., Medzihorská, M., Shoda-Kagaya, E., Martin, G. D., Sopow, S., Kochi, K. & Liebhold, A. M. (2024). The demise of enemy release associated with the invasion of specialist folivores on an invasive tree. *Ecography*, 2024(5), e07082. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecog.07082>

Mally, R., Turner, R. M., Bertelsmeier, C. & Liebhold, A. M. (under review) Darwin's naturalization conundrum in insects.

Paolo Tizzani –WOAH – Senior Veterinary Epidemiologist

Topic: The World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) journey from official animal health information to epidemic intelligence to Horizon scanning

Summary: WOAHA was originally established as the Office International des Epizooties in 1924, following an international agreement aimed at combating infectious animal diseases. The organisation operates in solidarity with its 183 Members with the common mission of avoiding international spread of animal diseases and therefore improve animal health globally.

Since its creation, WOAHA has evolved to adapt to the dynamic movement of pathogens at a global level, by moving towards a scanning approach and strengthening collaborations.

- 1994: creation of the Working Group for Wildlife in 1994, with an advisory role about health problems relating to wild animals.
- 2002: constitution of a team dedicated to monitoring non-official information.
- 2006: the Global Early Warning System (GLEWS+) network (One Health intelligence network between WOAHA, WHO and FAO).
- 2017: the enhanced GLEWS+ framework integrates the use of EIOS for broader, automated, and real-time intelligence.
- 2022: foundation of the Data Integration Department with the scope of connecting the different data collected.
- 2024: the Emerging Diseases Group starts scanning potential emerging diseases and advising WOAHA on how to react and adapt policies.
- 2025: activation of the Incident Management System with the aim of improving the emergencies management by WOAHA.

To perform HS, it is essential to aggregate information from epidemic intelligence, as well as both official and non-official sources. This approach helps to manage current risks, and also to prepare for potential, unforeseen risks. Official sources provide the necessary background and baseline for monitoring anomalies. WOAHA benefits from a database built on official data since 2005, enabling the identification of trends over time and across regions. Additionally, by integrating data from other sources (e.g., non-official channels) the sensitivity of the official reporting system is enhanced, as it not only completes existing knowledge but also brings in new, unofficial information. The World Animal Health Information System (WAHIS) gathers data on 121 notifiable diseases from various channels. This information is then verified, validated,

and synthesised into a report that communicates the current situation and highlights trends for the monitored diseases. One of the systems used to enhance WAHIS sensitivity is the EIOS system, which was originally designed for human health. A challenge of EIOS is to address gaps in regional coverage, as there is varying capacity to penetrate, detect signals, news, etc., in some areas where official sources are not as abundant. At the same time, efforts are being made to better shape EIOS for animal health. Other future challenges include carrying out this exercise while seeking to monitor and filter scenarios for One Health. Sharing data from a One Health perspective is truly key to further improving WOA's ability to detect known and unknown threats. Progress in this area includes integrating artificial intelligence to generate news summaries from diverse sources and improving translations of news headlines.

Keywords: animal health information, epidemic intelligence, infectious animal diseases, international agreement.

References:

FAO-WHO-WOAH. (2013). GLEWS+ The Joint FAO-OIE-WHO Global Early Warning System for health threats and emerging risks at the human-animal-ecosystems interface. *Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations*. <https://openknowledge.fao.org/items/a777b5da-5e4d-4280-8e31-ac1f65970554>

World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH). (2026). WAHIS: World Animal Health Information System. *WAHIS*. <https://wahis.woah.org>

Paula Castro – Centre for Functional Ecology, Coimbra University - Ecologist

Topic: *Co-creating Resilient Landscapes: Ecosystem Services, Stakeholders, Businesses and Technology Transfer*

Summary: The presentation aimed to provide an overview of her most recent professional years, highlighting how integrated work across these institutions has fostered knowledge sharing and participatory approaches to promote realistic, place-based solutions to complex environmental and regional challenges. She seeks to bring companies, associations, and other stakeholders closer to the scientific and technological system, promoting innovation, business competitiveness, and sustainable territorial development.

Project 1 – Cultivar: Competence Network for sustainable development and innovation in the agri-food sector. The Cultivar Project was funded under the Portugal 2020 framework, which is part of the European Union Structural and Investment Funds. The project was supported as an Integrated Programme of Scientific Research and Technological Development (R&D), aiming to strengthen innovation and territorial development in Portugal's Centro Region. The Cultivar Project responded to the major challenges faced by the agri-food sector in low-density areas of Portugal's Centro Region through an holistic territorial development strategy, aiming at characterising, conserving, and valorising endogenous genetic resources; Promoting collaboration between science, technology, and higher education institutions and the agri-food cluster; Strengthening regional competences and human capital; Implementing an innovative, holistic research methodology and Identifying new applications and value chains for endogenous plant resources,

Project 2 – Phoenix was funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 programme and aimed to increase democratic participation of citizens to support the European Green Deal. It included 11 pilot studies in 7 EU countries at different administrative scales. A transboundary study was also conducted between Portugal and Spain: this region faces common environmental challenges exacerbated by climate change, such as drought and wildfire risk.

Across related projects like Phoenix, she coordinated and integrated efforts, fostering participatory processes and co-creating sustainable development strategies. This included engaging stakeholders in landscape governance initiatives, particularly in fire-prone territories, and highlighting the role of traditional land management and rural economic activities in reducing fire risk and enhancing ecosystem resilience. These projects emphasised dialogue among scientists, local actors, associations, and practitioners to support realistic, place-based solutions to environmental and territorial challenges.

CR INOVE - Regional Innovation Catalyst for the Centre Region (Portugal) is an innovative regional initiative led by CCDRC to promote the innovation ecosystem in the Centre Region (Portugal) by encouraging interaction between scientific and technological entities and the business community, supporting pilot projects and collaborative networks. Main tasks include:

- Technology and Knowledge Transfer - CR Inove actively maps and mobilises technologies developed within universities, polytechnics, research centres, and technology transfer offices, making them accessible to companies, facilitating the commercialisation and practical application of scientific and technological knowledge, especially for SMEs with limited access to R&D resources.

- Identification and Resolution of Business Innovation Challenges - A core initiative of CR Inove is the identification of concrete innovation challenges faced by companies and matched with appropriate solutions from the scientific and technological system. Since its launch, CR Inove has identified more than 80 business and technological challenges and supported negotiation processes to address them.

- Matchmaking, Partnerships and Networking - acts as a neutral broker between companies, research institutions, public bodies, and innovation intermediaries to promote strategic partnerships between companies and R&D entities, networking events and brokerage sessions, and Interregional and cross-sector collaboration.

By 2024, the initiative had established more than 40 formal partnerships and supported dozens of collaborative negotiations. One of the case studies was the plant disease known as fire blight, which is affecting endogenous pear trees, especially in the western region. Information was systematically collected, and the next step is to share it with the community to support the identification of solutions. It is planned as an integrated approach across the ecosystem, species, and landscape governance levels, which is a major challenge.

The common goal of the presented projects is to find collective solutions, whether the problem is plant health or territorial sustainable development, involving all interested parties. Bottom-up approaches yielded a valuable strategy for identifying realistic, practical solutions.

Keywords: research, innovation, citizen engagement, ecosystem services, collaborative innovation networks, scalability, sustainable development

References:

CCDR – the Regional Coordination and Development Commission of the Central Region. (2026). *CR Inove*. CENTRO. <https://www.ccdrc.pt/en/cr-inove/>

CFE (2026) <https://cfe.uc.pt/>

Cultivar. (2022). Cultivar. https://icultivar.pt/en/home_en/

Farmer's perceptions of ecosystem services of agricultural landscapes: Are they the bad or the good guys? (n.d.). *Cultivar*. Retrieved 11 March 2026, from <https://icultivar.pt/en/projetos/farmers-perceptions-of-ecosystem-services-of-agricultural-landscapes-are-they-the-bad-or-the-good-guys/>

Phoenix (2026) Phoenix- Fondazione Giangiacomo Feltrinelli. <https://phoenix-horizon.eu/project/>

Paula, A., Frazao, L., Castro, P., Pulido, F., Pedro, S., Figueiredo, A. & Allegretti, G. (2025). Gobernanza de paisajes transfronterizos resilientes a los incendios forestales – caso de estudio de las Sierras de Gata y Malcata. Actas del Noveno Congreso Forestal Español, *Sociedad Española de Ciencias Forestales*. 1–15. https://ces.uc.pt/myces/UserFiles/livros/4184_9cfe-1467_Paulaetal.pdf

Mosaico (2026). Mosaico - Fire Smart Territories. Universidad de Extremadura. <https://mosaico-land.com/>

Pedro Gómez López – Segura Centre for Soil Science and Applied Biology (CEBAS-CSIC) - PhD. Research Scientist

Topic: Unveiling and tracking hidden plant viral disease invasion. Case study: poleroviruses spreading through cucurbit crops

Summary: The Epidemiology and Evolutionary Ecology of Viral Pathogens laboratory (EPEEV Lab) is integrated within the Plant Pathology group at CEBAS-CSIC (Spain) and combines descriptive, exploratory, and applied research approaches to understand, prevent, and effectively respond to the growing threat of pests and viral diseases in vegetable crops. Specifically, the lab conducts research on i) plant viral disease epidemiology, ii) the ecological and evolutionary mechanisms underlying viral dynamics, and iii) microbial-mediated biocontrol strategies for sustainable disease management (EPEEV lab, 2026).

In the context of this workshop, and focusing on the descriptive approach, this contribution aimed to discuss the characterization of the viral diseases affecting cucurbit crops, their impact and economic relevance across the Mediterranean Basin and Europe, with Spain as the leading producer, as well as the factors that may promote disease outbreaks or the emergence of viral diseases. Since over 70 viruses can infect cucurbit hosts, and several of them can remain latent without visible symptoms, or because different viruses may produce similar symptoms, a critical challenge arises: *how can new viruses or introduction events be detected early enough to timely respond and prevent their further spread?*

With this question in mind, the EPEEV lab has implemented systematic monitoring of symptomatic cucurbit crops. Epidemiological data spanning the last 12 years were presented, highlighting how over the last three seasons, a high proportion of watermelon plants exhibiting

yellowing symptoms tested negative for the full range of known viruses screened (Rabadán *et al.*, 2021, 2023, de Moya-Ruiz *et al.*, 2023). A further sequence-independent detection approach led to the identification of an unknown virus, *Polerovirus PABYV*, reported for first time in Spain. Thanks to the systematic monitoring and archived cucurbit sample collection from the long-term surveillance, a retrospective analysis revealed that this new virus had already emerged in 2018 and is now widely distributed across cucurbit crops. Its presence had likely gone undetected due to the similarity of its yellowing symptoms to those caused by the close-related polerovirus CABYV (de Moya-Ruiz *et al.* 2023).

Beyond virus detection, characterizing the genetic diversity of viral populations offers a powerful means to understand and track the evolutionary and population dynamics of viruses in real time, enabling the identification of recombination events and variants with potentially altered biological properties. Thus, it was also considered as phylodynamic approaches, integrating viral epidemiology, population genetics, and ecology, can help determine the origin of a virus, how rapidly it is spreading, and where it may emerge next, thereby supporting practical risk management. These aspects were further discussed in relation to other cucurbit viruses, reinforcing the case for a multi-layered surveillance framework.

Taken together, maintaining systematic surveillance to establish epidemiological baselines and detect anomalies, preserving seasonal samples for retrospective analysis, conducting phylogenetic studies to assess genetic diversity and population structure, and applying phylodynamic analyses to uncover transmission routes and evolutionary patterns are becoming indispensable tools. Their integration is essential for the development of effective, evidence-based, and sustainable plant disease management strategies.

Keywords: molecular epidemiology, phylodynamic, plant virus, systematic crop surveillance, virology.

References:

Rabadán, M.P., Juárez, M. & Gómez, P. (2023). Long-term monitoring of aphid-transmitted viruses in melon and zucchini crops: genetic diversity and population structure of cucurbit aphid-borne yellows virus and watermelon mosaic virus. *Phytopathology* 113, 1761. <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO-10-22-0394-V>

Rabadán, M.P. & Gómez, P. (2023). Global phylodynamics of two relevant aphid-transmitted viruses in cucurbit crops: cucurbit aphid-borne yellows virus and watermelon mosaic virus. *Phytopathology Research* 5, 53. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42483-023-00207-8>

De Moya-Ruiz, C., Juárez, M. & Gómez, P. (2023). First report of pepo aphid-borne yellows virus on watermelon plants in Spain. *New Disease Reports*, 48(1), e12215. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ndr2.12215>

EPEEV Lab. (n.d.). EPEEV Lab - Epidemiology and Evolutionary Ecology of Plant Viral Diseases. Retrieved 30 January 2026, from <https://pgomezlopez.wordpress.com/>

Riccardo Scalera – Department of Science, Roma Tre University - IUCN SSC Invasive Species Specialist Group - IUCN SSC Wildlife Health Specialist Group

Topic: Horizon scanning for biological invasions: challenges and opportunities

Summary: Biological invasions are a primary driver of global biodiversity loss, often acting in synergy with climate change and habitat destruction. As confirmed recently by the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES, 2023), invasive alien species (IAS) impact not only ecosystems but also human health and economic activities. While much focus is placed on the species themselves, IAS also act as subtle and pervasive drivers for the spread of pathogens by serving as hosts, vectors, or facilitators (see Scalera 2022, Pabst *et al.* 2025, IPBES 2023). Despite their impact, alien pathogens affecting wildlife often receive less attention than traditional drivers such as the international wildlife trade.

A fundamental element of managing invasions is understanding pathways, which reflect the human activities responsible for species movement (Harrower *et al.* 2020). Unlike other fields that define a "vector" as the species itself, invasion ecology focuses on the underlying human activity. Targeting these pathways allows for effective engagement with stakeholders and the development of preventative guidance.

The good news is that biological invasions are often reversible if addressed in time (McGeoch *et al.* 2010). Eradication and control remain some of the most effective conservation actions available (Langhammer *et al.* 2024). In the European Union, this is supported by a robust legislative framework, most notably Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014, which focuses on "species of Union concern". Because risk assessments for this listing process would be long and resource-intensive, horizon scanning is essential to prioritize which species would require urgent evaluation.

The European Commission conducted two major EU-wide horizon-scanning exercises in 2015 (Roy *et al.* 2015) and 2026 (Nunes *et al.* 2026) to derive prioritized lists of IAS for the coming decade. Both utilized the Delphi method, a structured consensus-building approach (MacMillan and Marshall 2006; Sutherland *et al.* 2011). The process consisted of two distinct phases:

1. Preliminary consultation: experts within five thematic groups (plants, vertebrates, terrestrial invertebrates, marine, and freshwater) conduct literature reviews and provide preliminary scores.
2. Consensus workshop: experts meet in person to moderate scores across groups and reach a final agreement.

Species were scored based on four primary criteria: i) likelihood of arrival, ii) likelihood of establishment, iii) likelihood of spread after establishment, and iv) potential impact to biodiversity.

The primary challenge is the sheer volume of potential invaders. In the most recent exercise by Nunes *et al.* (2026), an initial longlist of 8,857 species was filtered down to 4,053 for assessment. This reduction relies on removing species with clear climate mismatches or a lack of invasion history. While Nunes *et al.* (2026) attempted to automate parts of this screening using Species Distribution Models (SDMs) and GBIF climate matching, the results highlighted the limits of automation. Incomplete baseline data often lead to unreliable outputs, and models frequently fail to capture complex ecological requirements. This reinforces a critical lesson: expert scrutiny is essential at every stage. Automated tools are useful for flagging potential risks, but they

cannot yet replace the nuanced judgment of a cross-disciplinary expert network. Of the species assessed in the latest cycle, 622 were discussed at the consensus workshop, resulting in 57 species being classified as "very high risk" and 108 as "high risk" (Nunes *et al.* 2026).

A sobering example of the gap between assessment and implementation is the red imported fire ant (*Solenopsis invicta*) (Menchetti *et al.* 2023). Although it was already risk-assessed by the European Commission in 2017 (Kenis *et al.* 2017) following an earlier horizon scanning (Roy *et al.* 2015) and eventually listed as a species of Union concern in 2022, it had been introduced unintentionally in Sicily since at least 2019. However, its detection in Sicily was not reported until years after its establishment (Menchetti *et al.* 2023). Interestingly, soon after, the species was also evaluated by the EFSA Panel on Plant Health (see EFSA, 2023). This case proves that even the best scientific tools are ineffective without adequate enforcement and prompt information flow (Genovesi *et al.* 2024).

Beyond taxonomic groups, in the field of biological invasions, horizon scanning has also been applied to identify knowledge gaps regarding alien pathogens (Roy *et al.* 2017). A 2015 exercise involving 39 experts identified 10 key areas for research, shifting the focus from specific diseases to the systematic lack of epidemiological data for wildlife.

Moving forward, the primary goal of horizon scanning is to translate scientific foresight into immediate legislative action. Given the clear parallels between biological invasions and plant/animal health frameworks, future efforts should focus on:

- Harmonizing cross-sectoral tools: aligning horizon-scanning methodologies across plant health and invasion ecology to create a unified defence against new threats.
- Bridging the science-policy gap: ensuring that "high-risk" classifications trigger mandatory rapid-response protocols to prevent establishment.
- Broadening the taxonomic lens: expanding scanning efforts to include overlooked "subtle" threats, such as alien pathogens and parasites.

By repositioning IAS management as a central pillar of biodiversity strategy rather than a standalone task, we can leverage cross-disciplinary networks to protect global ecosystems more effectively. Harmonizing objectives and ensuring prompt information flow remain the most critical steps in transforming these prioritized lists into tangible conservation outcomes.

Keywords: biodiversity losses, biological invasions, IAS, introduction pathways.

References:

Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2022/1203 of 12 July 2022 Amending Implementing Regulation (EU) 2016/1141 to Update the List of Invasive Alien Species of Union Concern, L 186/10 (2022). https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg_impl/2022/1203/oj/eng

EFSA Panel on Plant Health (PLH), Bragard, C., Baptista, P., Chatzivassiliou, E., Di Serio, F., Gonthier, P., Jaques Miret, J. A., Justesen, A. F., Magnusson, C. S., Milonas, P., Navas-Cortes, J. A., Parnell, S., Potting, R., Reignault, P. L., Stefani, E., Thulke, H., Van der Werf, W., Vicent Civera, A., Yuen, J., Zappalà, L., Grégoire, J.-C., Malumphy, C., Kertesz, V., Maiorano, A. & MacLeod, A. (2023). Pest categorisation of *Solenopsis invicta*. *EFSA Journal*, 21(5). <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2023.7998>

Genovesi, P., Carnevali, L., Hoffmann, B. D., Monaco, A., Roy, H. E. & Simberloff, D. (2024). Conservation action should come before publication. *Current Biology*, 34(2), R49–R51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2023.11.054>

Harrower, C. A., Scalera, R., Pagad, S., Schönrogge, K. & Roy, H. E. (2020). Guidance for interpretation of the CBD categories of pathways for the introduction of invasive alien species. *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2779/6172>

IPBES. (2023). Thematic assessment report on invasive alien species and their control of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (Roy, H. E., Pauchard, A., Stoett, P., and Renard Truong, T. (eds.); Version 4). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany - *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430682>

Kenis, M., Rabitsch, W. & Roy, H. (2017). Annex 7: Risk Assessment for *Solenopsis invicta* Buren, 1972. In Study on Invasive Alien Species – Development of risk assessments to tackle priority species and enhance prevention. *European Commission*

European Commission. (2026, March 9). Invasive alien species—Environment -. *Environment*. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/nature-and-biodiversity/invasive-alien-species_en

International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources. (2026). *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species*. *IUCN Red List*. <https://www.iucnredlist.org/en>

Invasive Species Specialist Group ISSG. (2015). 100 of the World's Worst Invasive Alien Species [Database]. *Global Invasive Species Database*. https://www.iucngisd.org/gisd/100_worst.php

Langhammer, P. F., Bull, J. W., Bicknell, J. E., Oakley, J. L., Brown, M. H., Bruford, M. W., Butchart, S. H. M., Carr, J. A., Church, D., Cooney, R., Cutajar, S., Foden, W., Foster, M. N., Gascon, C., Geldmann, J., Genovesi, P., Hoffmann, M., Howard-McCombe, J., Lewis, T., Macfarlane, N. B. W., Melvin, Z. E., Stoltz Merizalde, R., Morehouse, M. G., Pagad, S., Polidoro, B., , Sechrest, W., , Segelbacher, G., Smith, K. G, Steadman, J., Strongin, K., Williams, J., Woodley, S. & Brooks, T. M. (2024). The positive impact of conservation action. *Science*, 384(6694), 453–458. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adj6598>

McGeoch, M. A., Butchart, S. H. M., Spear, D., Marais, E., Kleynhans, E. J., Symes, A., Chanson, J. & Hoffmann, M. (2010). Global indicators of biological invasion: Species numbers, biodiversity impact and policy responses. *Diversity and Distributions*, 16, 95–108. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-4642.2009.00633.x>

Menchetti, M., Schifani, E., Alicata, A., Cardador, L., Sbrega, E., Toro-Delgado, E. & Vila, R. (2023). The invasive ant *Solenopsis invicta* is established in Europe. *Current Biology*, 33(17), R896–R897. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2023.07.036>

Nunes AL, Venter TS, Adriaens T, Bond GM, Costello KE, Delva S, Gospodinov K, Novoa A, Peyton J, Pyšek P, Rabitsch W, Roy HE, Scalera R, Smith KE, Tricarico E, Aldridge D, Altamirano M, Bellotto V, Bertolino S, Brundu G, Cardoso AC, Cavadino I, Dawson W, Demetriou J, Devisscher S, D'hondt B, Essl F, Evans T, Everts T, Gallardo B, García-Berthou E, Groom Q, Hillaert J, Jacobs A, Katsanevakis S, Marchante E, Marchini A, Oficialdegui FJ, Olenin S, O'Riordan RM, Pattison Z, Petersen F, Preda C, Rebelo R, Reniers J, Scheers K, Skuhrovec J, Solarz W, Steen F, Strubbe D, Van Landuyt W, van Valkenburg J, Verëll V, Verhelst P & Verreycken H. (2025). Invasive Alien Species Horizon Scanning in support of implementation of Regulation 1143/2014 - Final Study Report and Supplementary files. Prepared under Service contract 09.0201/2023/907919/SER/ENV.D2 for the European Commission. *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://doi.org/10.2779/7146677>

Pabst, R., Sousa, C. A., Essl, F., García-Rodríguez, A., Liu, D., Lenzner, B., Schertler, A., Zêzere, J. L. & Capinha, C. (2025). Global invasion patterns and dynamics of disease vector mosquitoes. *Nature Communications*, 16, 9127. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-025-64446-3>

Regulation (EU) No 1143/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 October 2014 on the prevention and management of the introduction and spread of invasive alien species <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2014/1143/oj/eng>

Directorate-General for Environment (European Commission), CEH (Centre of Ecology & Hydrology), Roy HE, Adriaens T, Aldridge DC, Bacher S, Bishop JDD, Blackburn TM, Branquart E, Brodie J, Carboneras C, Cook EJ, Copp GH, Dean HJ, Eilenberg J, Essl F, Gallardo B, Garcia M, García-Berthou E, Genovesi P, Hulme PE, Kenis M, Kerckhof F, Kettunen M, Minchin D, Nentwig W, Nieto A, Pergl J, Pescott O, Peyton J, Preda C, Rabitsch W, Roques A, Rorke S, Scalera R, Schindler S, Schönrogge K, Sewell J, Solarz W, Stewart A, Tricarico E, Vanderhoeven S, van der Velde G, Vilà M, Wood CA & Zenetos A (2015). Invasive alien species: Prioritising prevention efforts through horizon scanning: final report. *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2779/096586>

Roy, H. E., Hesketh, H., Purse, B. V., Eilenberg, J., Santini, A., Scalera, R., Stentiford, G. D., Adriaens, T., Bacela-Spychalska, K., Bass, D., Beckmann, K. M., Bessell, P., Bojko, J., Booy, O., Cardoso, A. C., Essl, F., Groom, Q., Harrower, C., Kleespies, R., Martinou AF, van Oers MM, Peeler EJ, Pergl J, Rabitsch W, Roques A, Schaffner F, Schindler S, Schmidt BR, Schonrogge K, Smith J, Solarz W, Stewart A, Stroo A, Tricarico E, Vannini A, Vila M, Woodward S, Wynns AA & Dunn, A. M. (2017). Alien Pathogens on the Horizon: Opportunities for Predicting their Threat to Wildlife. *Conservation Letters*, 10(4), 477–484. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12297>

Scalera, R. (2022). Report on alien pathogens and pathogens spread by invasive alien species in Europe. T-PVS/Inf (2022) 40 *Council of Europe, Strasbourg*, 26. <https://rm.coe.int/inf40e-2022-report-on-alien-pathogens/1680a7bcc9>

Sutherland, W. J., Fleishman, E., Mascia, M. B., Pretty, J. & Rudd, M. A. (2011). Methods for collaboratively identifying research priorities and emerging issues in science and policy. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 2(3), 238–247. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2041-210X.2010.00083.x>

Kenisha Garnett – PhD Cranfield University

Topic: AI-driven horizon scanning methodology

Summary: Project funded by the Department for Science, Innovation and Technology

UK Government Authors: Alice Johnston, Kenisha Garnett, Alison Parker, Ian Truckell, Ann Holden, Professor Stephen Hallett, Dr Theresa Mercer, Dr Xinyue Cui, Dr Abdou Khouakhi and Dr Simon Jude.

High-level overview of outputs: This project explores how AI can be integrated into HS to strengthen the identification, assessment, and prioritisation of emerging risks relevant to public policy challenges. Responding to the growing volume, speed, and uncertainty of information surrounding complex policy issues, the study addressed limitations in traditional, largely manual scanning approaches, particularly concerns around efficiency, transparency, and evidence needed to provide confidence in policy decision-making.

The core output of the project is a conceptual framework for a semi-automated HS methodology that combines AI-enabled automation with expert judgement. Rather than replacing human expertise, the framework is designed as a hybrid system that maximises automation where it adds value, while retaining expert input at critical interpretive and decision-making stages. This approach aims to improve scalability and consistency while maintaining credibility and policy relevance of scan outputs.

At a high level, the framework produces four interlinked stages AI-enabled HS:

1. Dynamic scan database that continuously captures and organises diverse information sources, including both established trends and weak signals. Automated tools that support data collection, categorisation and textual summary to ensure scan outputs remain current and accessible.
2. Scenarios that synthesise trends and weak signals into plausible future developments. Automation assists with pattern recognition and mapping interdependencies, while expert validation ensures scenarios are meaningful within the policy context and appropriately reflect uncertainty.
3. Prioritised scenarios aligned with government policy objectives. Quantitative scoring and qualitative ratings are combined to highlight which issues (scenarios) warrant attention across different time horizons. Automated calculations and visualisations support transparency and consistency, while expert judgement provides contextual nuance.

Targeted deep-dive analyses that translate scanning insights into actionable policy understanding. These deep dives support short-to-medium and longer-term decision-making by examining trade-offs, possible solutions, and broader social, ethical, and policy implications.

The project demonstrates how AI-based tools can enhance HS by improving efficiency, traceability and responsiveness to rapid change. The outputs provide a foundation for more confident use of HS as an evidence base to support policy decisions, while recognising the continued importance of human oversight in managing uncertainty and value-based judgements.

Keywords: AI, emerging risks, horizon scanning, hybrid approach, weak signals.

References: Latest foresight papers and projects:

British Council. (2022). Foresight into the Bio-circular green Economy. *British Council*. <https://www.britishcouncil.or.th/en/programmes/education/our-work-support-higher-education-and-research-sectorname/going-global>

Garnett, K., Delgado, J., Lickorish, F. A., Pollard, S. J. T., Medina-Vaya, A., Magan, N., Leinster, P. & Terry, L. A. (2023). Future foods: Morphological scenarios to explore changes in the UK food system with implications for food safety across the food chain. *Futures*, 149, 103140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2023.103140>

University of Geneva. (2024, November 30). Shaping environmental policy in the pan-European region applying foresight methodologies. *Geneva Science-Policy Interface*. <https://www.gspi.ch/collaboration-projects/shaping-environmental-policy-in-the-pan-european-region-applying-foresight-methodologies>

Bellamy, A. S., Benton, T., Breeze, T. D., Brooks, J., Campbell, K., Doherty, B., Elahi, S., Falloon, P., Frewer, L., Garnett, K., Gregory, P. J., Hasnain, S., Hayes, A., Ingram, J., Jackson, P., Johnstone, A., Lambie-Mumford, H., Lonnie, M., Loopstra, R., McDermott, K., Noble, I., Parsons,

K., Power, M., Thomas, M. & Wagstaff, C. (2024). United Kingdom Food Security Report 2024. UK Government. <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/united-kingdom-food-security-report-2024>

Garnett, K., Wilson, A. & Wilkinson, E. (2025). Using Horizon Scanning to Build Policy Resilience: Case of Waste Crime. *Futures & Foresight Science*, 7(1), e201. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ffo2.201>

Directorate-General for Environment (European Commission), White, O., Garnett, K., Zamparutti, T., & Sadauskis, R. (2023). The EU environmental foresight system (FORENV): Final report of 2021 22 annual cycle: emerging environmental issues due to demographic changes in the EU. *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2779/495525>

Challenge of the workshop

To complement and consolidate the large amount of information generated during the presentations and to favour interactions among participants, several engaging moments were organised throughout the workshop.

During the first day, an ice-breaking session was held to define the participants' expertise and their prior knowledge on risk drivers. This second aspect was checked again on the third day, to observe if any progression was achieved during the event.

The core hands-on activity was represented by the polycrisis exercise, which took place during the morning of the second day.

Finally, at the end of the third day, the meeting was wrapped up, adding information gathered by "ghost rapporteurs" during the event and allowing for a brainstorming moment among all participants.

All the activities are described in more detail below.

Polycrisis exercise

The Polycrisis Exploration Workshop was run by Lydia Caldana and Caroline Parquet from the JRC Unit S.1 - Innovation in Science and Policymaking - EU Policy Lab: Foresight, Design & Behavioural Insights. This tool is based on the Risks on the Horizon foresight study⁷ where 40 emerging risks⁸ were identified as potential hazards for humanity (Muench *et al.*, 2024)⁹. For this workshop, the exercise was targeted to Plant Health with a time horizon of 10 years.

During this session, all probable scenarios were conceived to get a broader view (**Figure 2**) of plant health future.

Figure 2. The "future cone"-adapted from Hancock and Bezold (1994)¹⁰

⁷ Accessible from <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC137493>

⁸ https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/polycrisis-toolkit_en

⁹ Muench, S., Whyte, J., Hauer, G., Maleville, A. & de, Asikainen, T. (2024). Risks on the horizon, *Publications Office of the European Union*. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/526889>

¹⁰ Hancock, T. & Bezold, C. (1994). Possible futures, preferable futures. *Healthcare Forum Journal*. 37, 23-29. <https://europepmc.org/article/med/10132155>

To gain an initial understanding of participants' perspective, they were asked some general questions. Firstly, they were invited to consider whether they thought the future in 2035 would be better or worse than the present. The responses were as follows: 8 participants (33%) believed the future would be better, while 16 (67%) felt it would be worse. Participants were also asked if they thought anything could be done to improve the situation, with 20 people (83%) responding 'yes' and 4 (17%) saying 'no'. Based on these answers, the participants were classified in three categories:

- red group: believed the future will be better and that positive action is possible (8 people, 33%)
- green: believed the future will be worse, but improvements can still be made (12 people, 50%)
- blue: believed the future will be worse and that nothing can be done to change (4 people, 17%)

Notably, no participants indicated that the future would be better but that nothing could be done to influence it.

Activity 1: "Enhance risk awareness by exploring the broad spectrum of risks"

For the first activity, 40 future risks were considered. These 40 risks are represented and summarized in form of cards provided by the facilitators: The visual approach allowed participants selecting and prioritizing risks of interest after having placed them in a chart where X axis represented the potential impact on plant health and Y axis the current knowledge about that risk (**Figure 3**). Next, all participants debated about the position of the cards, sharing arguments that take into account likelihood, availability of management options, etc.

The risks retained for the next step of the exercise were those represented by cards positioned on the bottom right of the Cartesian plan: risks with the potential of causing major consequences and low predictability and preparedness opportunities.

Figure 3. Chart displaying the 40 risk cards classified by their potential impact on plant health (X axis) and the knowledge available in 2025 for their impact in 2035 (y axis).

Finally, participants voted the most relevant with that cluster for a total of 8 cards, including one blank card renamed "climate change" in order to include a risk considered very well known by the group but still representing one of the most crucial global threats directly affecting plant health already now but even more in the future. Those 8 cards were classified into three categories⁸ (**Figure 4**):

1. Extreme natural events: i) environmental disasters and ii) climate change
2. Extreme violence / narratives: iii) terrorism and iv) civil war in the EU
3. Weak democratic governance: v) loss of democratic values, vi) inefficient decision-making processes, vii) collapse of democratic governments and viii) inadequate regulations for emerging events

Those crises were used for the next activity.

1. Extreme natural events

2. Extreme violence / narratives

3. Weak democratic governance

Figure 4. Final selection of risk cards with potential high impact on plant health and low current knowledge available.

Activity 2: "Map future potential polycrisis and explore interconnected (cascading) impacts"

For activity 2, participants were divided in two groups with an equal composition in terms of personal perspective of the future (see red, green and blue groups mentioned in the introduction of the polycrisis exercise).

Each group had to imagine a scenario in 10 years where selected risks (the three risks resulting from the combination of the eight selected risk cards, as described above in Activity 1 and Figure 4) produce cascading and connected effects. This was achieved by drawing a map on a poster. For each risk the participants identified and described a series of impacts to the plant health domain following the STEEP framework (Social, Technological, Ethical, Environmental, Political/Economic) (**Figure 5**).

At last, each group was requested to identify the most concerning scenarios and to draw connections between effects. This allowed the group to identify causal loops and hotspots (i.e. impacts with many connections) within their scenario.

The polycrisis maps obtained by the two groups allowed highlighting a number of points of common interest between the two groups, emerging simultaneously from multiple nodes in the cascade of impacts:

- Rise of individualism and/or loss of empathy would emerge as societal risks from the crises, favouring divisions and anarchist positions.
- The crucial role of local agricultural productions in response to food insecurity.
- The consequences to funding cuts for research activities, expected in crisis situation, pair with breaks in technology and access to information.

In summary, participants generally agreed that, in the event of extreme or global crises, plant health would likely become a lower priority aspect for policy makers. This shift would result from several interconnected factors: i) the reduction of available resources, ii) increased polarization between scientific perspectives and popular opinion, leading to diminished trust in the role of science iii) the long-term strain of emergency conditions, and iv) a decline in the effect of diplomacy.

Figure 5. Future Polycrisis Maps.

Interactive session results

Two Mentimeter sessions were held alongside presentations and exercises to assess participants' knowledge and perspective at the beginning of the workshop and potential shifts at the end of event.

Participants answered background questions:

- their interest in plant health (55% yes, 45% no)
- foresight experience (80% yes, 20% no).
- personal expertise, presented in a word cloud, to showcase the group's diversity (**Figure 6**).

Figure 6. Word cloud displaying the 59 answers from 23 participants to the question “Which is the main topic you work on?”

The following questions aimed to explore the topic of risk drivers in greater depth. First, participants were asked to name all risk drivers they were aware of. Among the 50 answers, the most frequently mentioned was trade (listed 8 times), followed by climate change, human actions, and migration. Additional drivers cited included biological invasions, commodities, biodiversity, geopolitical situation and tourism. When asked which of these factors they considered in their daily work, trade again stood out as the most prominent, followed by climate. Biological invasions and human behaviour were also noted.

These two questions were asked again on the third day, with slightly different results. This second time, the total number of answers was 64, where trade, followed by climate change and alien species, was still recorded as the most mentioned. However, new drivers not appearing in the previous round were noted: land use, disinformation, cargos and harbour rules. While other drivers were mentioned more times: societal changes, political instability, conflicts. Regarding the use of those drivers at work, participants were asked which ones they would include in their work from now on. Trade confirmed to be the most popular, followed by bioterrorism, land use changes and conflicts.

For next question, the risk drivers for plant health were proposed in four general categories: biological, climatic, social, economic risk drivers. All participants were then requested to position each category in a Cartesian plan based on the potential impact on entry and establishment of an invasive pest into a new area (with a scoring system from 1 to 100). This question was

repeated at the beginning, then at the end of the event: consistently, the 'human' risk drivers (social and economic) were expected to affect more the entry, while the 'natural' risk drivers (biological and climatic) to affect more the establishment. What changed between the first and second round was an increase in the expected impact to entry due to biological, climatic and economic risk drivers (**Figure 7**).

Figure 7. Distribution of risk driver categories influencing establishment and entry of plant pests. X axis corresponds to the impact on the establishment and Y axis corresponds to impact on the entry. Each dot averages the score given by all users for each category to both impacts (1st answer n = 22; 2nd answer n=19).

Lastly, the following two questions were asked only on the third day, once participants had gathered more knowledge about risk drivers:

- Effect of risk drivers on plant pests should be considered at:
 - ecosystem,
 - taxon,
 - species level;
- Effect of risk drivers should be considered over a period of:
 - months,
 - quarters,
 - years.

Participants replied by quantifying the relevance of each component with a score from 0 to 100. The results are shown in **figure 8**.

Effect of risk drivers should be considered over a period of...

Effect of drivers on plant pests should be considered at...

Figure 8. In which way the effect of risk drivers should be integrated in the HS activity. What would be the most suitable time frame (up) and granularity (down).

Dynamic wrap up/overview

To dynamically capture the conclusions of the event, on the third day we obtained feedback from participants through the 'tree game', and gathered the perspectives collected by the 'ghost rapporteurs' in a way to share the observations collected during the whole duration of the workshop.

Visual feedback (tree game)

To measure the level of satisfaction on different perspectives, the participants were asked to decorate a tree with different coloured balls. The parameters measured were:

- 1) Overall satisfaction: number of balls placed;
- 2) Learning and knowledge: number of balls in the upper part;
- 3) Networking, communication and sharing: number of balls in the middle part;
- 4) Relevance: number of balls in the bottom part.

After, the trees were distributed on the table, with the idea of composing a forest, based on the timeframe expected to engage each participant to the new knowledge acquired: from now (bottom, in the picture) to in the future (upper part of the picture).

Looking at the results for the trees (**Figure 9**), on all the trees, each section is decorated, with a good number of balls homogenously distributed. In general, there is a wide distribution of trees over the time frame, with a higher number closer to the present, that can be interpreted as the willingness for most of participant to engage with activities related to foresight in the near future.

Figure 9. On the left, schematic description of the features represented by the trees. On the right, picture of decorated trees and their time frame distribution performed on the last day of the workshop.

Ghost rapporteurs

At the beginning of the workshop, three participants were secretly tasked with identifying a set of three key words during the course of the event.

First set:

1. *WHAOU*: this onomatopoeia expresses how inspiring the event was perceived. Attendees were impressed by the depth of knowledge and the variety of methodologies already available for foresight analysis. However, they also recognized the need to further integrate and adapt this knowledge so it can be applied effectively to the field of plant health.
2. Diversity of expertise: the wide range of expertise among participants led to rich interactions. There was a shared realization that conducting meaningful foresight and horizon scanning analyses cannot be done in isolation. Capturing the complexity of plant health requires interdisciplinary collaboration.
3. Learn: there is an ongoing process to ensure anticipation and adaptation, which includes understanding complex systems (such as human and climate processes), adopting new technologies, and enhancing analytical capabilities to identify signals.

Second set:

1. Complexity: this word refers not just to risk drivers as a topic, but to the questions surrounding them. It addresses how we manage emerging changes and predict the consequences of global phenomena such as climate change, environmental disasters, biodiversity loss, and disruption in ecosystem services. These are multifaceted challenges numerous variables and possible outcomes. It is a significant challenge.
2. Means: how can we make complexity understandable? By using multicriteria analysis, data curation, AI, modelling tools, databases, etc. Throughout the workshop, participants emphasized the need to collect relevant data across multiple parameters and to aggregate it for analysis.
3. Network: the creation of a synergistic network is essential. This allows connections among different actors and data sources. Collecting local data is necessary for global analysis, information sharing, and integration of diverse datasets. Emerging technical risks highlight the importance of global collaboration to identify new risks through collective intelligence.

Third set:

1. Convergence (from day one): this word reflects the surprising convergence of diverse expertise, with all participants moving toward a common goal.
2. Challenges (from day two): this word highlights the many challenges to overcome, focusing on practical issues, future uncertainties, and strategies for addressing potential crises in plant health.
3. Opportunities (from day three): despite the challenges, there are multiple solutions in development, particularly involving AI, to enhance HS activities as a community.

Conclusions and recommendations

Building on almost a decade of experience in horizon scanning for plant health, EFSA has developed a robust and well-established framework for the early identification of emerging risks, significantly contributing to preparedness and timely risk management at EU level. In an increasingly complex and rapidly evolving global context, this solid foundation now calls for expanded knowledge and the exploration of complementary approaches, to ensure the continued relevance of the outputs. In particular, strengthening foresight activities and investigating alternative solutions are essential to further enhance anticipation capacities and preparedness for future plant health risks.

In this context, the overall outcome of the workshop was highly satisfactory. The diversity of knowledge presented, and the connections established across different topics, clearly highlighted the need to strengthen communication networks between disciplines in order to harmonise concepts and share data and tools. Events such as this workshop represent an important first step in this direction. To support the development of a proper One Health framework, the concept of ontology also emerged as essential.

The variety of disciplines and topics addressed during the workshop demonstrated that many of the analyses required are shared across domains, including the use and development of **tools** such as **artificial intelligence** and **databases**. These tools can be developed synergistically, enabling information to flow more effectively between disciplines and institutions. Overall, the discussions reinforced the need for a proactive approach to adapting to change in a dynamic and continuously evolving landscape.

In addressing future challenges, foresight exercises proved highly relevant to the field of plant health, including from a global perspective, thanks to their ability to encourage thinking **beyond disciplinary boundaries**, and to support the identification of creative solutions. The relevance of climate change as a major driver for plant health risks remains evident, although attention was also drawn to other global change pressures. This is the case for **trade**, for which a wealth of data is already available. Other important factors, which may be less straightforward to integrate but whose role is clearly significant, include **extreme natural events**, human driven events, **mass migrations**, and **disinformation**.

Therefore, the next phase in the evolution of plant health horizon scanning will require to investigate into how additional factors, such as trade and major events, can be integrated by taking advantage of new technologies, including AI, and increasingly reach and accessible databases, such as Copernicus. It will also require contributing to the development of a comprehensive and harmonized ontology system and maintaining close links with other health domains in order to ensure the proper positioning and relevance of plant health within the **One Health** context.

EFSA wishes to extend sincere thanks to all workshop participants for their valuable contributions, insightful perspectives and **enthusiastic engagement** throughout the event. Their commitment to advancing plant health and fostering collaborative dialogue has been instrumental in shaping the outcomes and recommendations presented here. Together, these efforts are helping to lay the groundwork for a **more resilient and integrated** health environment across Europe.

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANSES	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety
CABI	CAB International
EC	European Commission
ECDC	Epidemic Intelligence activities at the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EIOS	Epidemic Intelligence from Open Sources
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
HS	Horizon Scanning
IAS	Invasive Alien Species
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
JRC	Joint Research Centre
MSs	Member States
SLAs	Service-level agreements
WHO	World Health Organization
WOAH	World Organisation for Animal Health

Appendix A – List of participants

Name	Surname	Affiliation	Role
Adamantia	Athanasopoulou	JRC	Remote speaker
Pieter	Beck	JRC	Remote speaker
Caroline	Bellenot	ANSES	Organiser
Bernard	Bottex	EFSA	Participant
Lydia	Caldana	JRC	Trainer
Susan	Canavan	University of Galway	Participant
Ana Cristina	Cardoso	JRC	Remote speaker
Paula	Castro	University of Coimbra	Participant
Rui	Catarino	JRC	Remote speaker
James	Cullum	CAB International (CABI)	Participant
René	Eschen	Swiss Federal office for agriculture	Participant
Emmanuel	Gachet	ANSES	Organiser
Kenisha	Garnett	Cranfield University	Participant
Pedro	Gomez Lopez	CSIC	Participant
Nicolas	Lévêque	EC	Participant
Jens	Linge	JRC	Remote speaker
Richard	Mally	Czech University of Life Science	Participant
Zoé	Marmier	ANSES	Organiser
Alan	Mcleod	DEFRA	Participant
Lucie	Michel	INRAE	Participant
Lia	Orfei	JRC	Remote speaker
Maria Luisa	Paracchini	JRC	Remote speaker
Caroline	Parquet	JRC	Trainer
Karmen	Poljansek	JRC	Remote speaker
Philippe	Reignault	ANSES	Organiser
Maria	Ribaya	EFSA	Organiser
Mathieu	Roche	CIRAD	Participant
Riccardo	Scalera	Roma Tre University	Participant
Luigi	Spagnolo	JRC	Remote speaker
Gianfranco	Spiteri	ECDC	Participant
Paolo	Tizzani	WOAH	Participant
Francesca	Torti	JRC	Speaker
Sara	Tramontini	EFSA	Organiser
Adamo	Uboldi	JRC	Chairman
Danila	Volpi	JRC	Remote speaker
Sybre	Vos	EFSA	Organiser
Sofia	Windstam	Swedish Board of Agriculture	Participant

Appendix B – Agenda of the event

Tuesday 2 December

Risk drivers		
14:00 – 14:15	ANSES/EFSA introduction	Philippe Reignault Sybren Vos
14:15 – 14:30	EFSA Horizon Scanning activity	Sara, Zoé, Caroline
14:30 – 15:00	Ice breaking + tour de table	Everyone
	Aggregated Total Applied Toxicity indicator (ATAT)	Rui Catarino
15:00 – 15:30	Threats without borders: mosquito modelling for anticipatory risk analysis.	Lia Orfei
	Analysis of disinformation narratives using AI	Jens Linge
15:30 – 15:40	Buffer time	
	The future distribution of EU tree species.	Pieter Beck
15:40 – 16:15	Invasive alien species and biodiversity	Ana Cristina Cardoso
	Main risk drivers affecting ecosystem services	Maria Luisa Paracchini
16:15 – 16:35	Coffee break + posters	
	Risks in the built environment	Adamantia Athanasopoulou
16:35 – 17:15	The INFORM Framework for Risk Drivers of Humanitarian crisis	Karmen Poljansek
	Drought risk for vegetation and crop	Danila Volpi
17:15 – 17:35	Presentation (Trade)	Francesca Torti
19:00	<i>Cocktail – Au petit caporal</i>	

Wednesday 3 December

Interactive sessions		
9:30 – 11:00	Interactive session – Polycrisis exercise	Caroline Parquet Lydia Caldana
11:00 – 11:30	Coffee break + posters	
11:30 – 13:00	Interactive session – Polycrisis exercise	Caroline Parquet Lydia Caldana
13:00-14:30	Lunch	

14:30 – 15:30	CABI data, horizon scanning and risk monitoring	James Cullum
	Threat detection at ECDC	Gianfranco Spiteri
	EFSA's Emerging risks analysis and horizon scanning process	Bernard Bottex
	The French national plant health surveillance platform	Lucie Michel
15:30 – 16:00	Ontology	Luigi Spagnolo
16:00 – 16:30	Coffee break + posters	
16:30 – 17:00	Trades with EFSA	Francesca Torti
17:00 – 17:30	Macroecology and biogeography of global insect invasions	Richard Mally
	WOAH journey from official animal health information to epidemic intelligence to Horizon scanning	Paolo Tizzani
17:30 – 18:00	Wrap-up	
19:30	Social event – Le bistrot du peintre	

Thursday 4 December

Conclusions

9:00 – 09:30	Mentimeter session II	Everyone
09:30 – 10:30	Urban and Forest Ecosystem Department	Paula Castro
	Unveiling and tracking hidden plant viral disease invasion. Case study: poleroviruses spreading through cucurbit crops	Pedro Lopez
	Horizon scanning for biological invasions: challenges and opportunities to current practices	Riccardo Scalera
	AI-driven horizon scanning methodology	Kenisha Garnett
10:30 – 11:00	Coffee break + game	
11:00 – 11:30	Presentation	Lydia Caldana
11:30 – 13:00	Open discussion and wrap up	Everyone